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*Business Models Strategici per Living Labs: Progettare Ecosistemi
di Innovazione Sostenibili*

*Strategic Business Models for Living Labs:
Designing Sustainable Innovation Ecosystems*

RELATORE

Prof. Plinio Limata

Handwritten signature of Prof. Plinio Limata in black ink.

CORRELATORE

Prof. Matteo Rizzoli

CANDIDATO

Michelle Gonzalez Torres

Handwritten signature of Michelle Gonzalez Torres in blue ink.

Matricola: 27536/410

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ABSTRACT

Living Labs are open innovation ecosystems operating in real-life environments. They harness iterative feedback processes throughout the innovation lifecycle to create sustainable impact by actively engaging citizens, research organizations, companies, and government bodies. This thesis examines the evolution from traditional, closed innovation models to these dynamic, collaborative paradigms, demonstrating how Living Labs serve as critical environments for co-creation, rapid prototyping, testing, and scaling up innovations. A central contribution of this work is its focus on financial sustainability, an area often overlooked in the design and operation of Living Labs. By critically reviewing existing business model frameworks, the thesis identifies key factors influencing the economic viability of these ecosystems. Building on these insights, it introduces CanvasLab - a tailored Business Model Canvas specifically designed for Living Labs. CanvasLab integrates principles of co-creation, multi-stakeholder collaboration, and iterative innovation with financial performance metrics, offering a comprehensive tool for strategic decision-making. The proposed framework not only enhances the understanding of how Living Labs can generate and sustain value but also provides practical guidance for practitioners aiming to foster robust, financially sustainable innovation environments. This study thereby contributes to both the academic discourse on sustainable innovation ecosystems and the practical advancement of Living Lab methodologies.

1. From Closed Innovation to Co-Creation: Exploring Open and User Innovation Paradigms

1.1 What is Innovation?

In 1934 Schumpeter defined "innovation" as "new combinations" of new or existing knowledge, resources, technology, and other variables. In addition, Schumpeter believed innovation to involve the development of new technologies or the finding of different applications for existing technologies, as well as their implementation into existing or new goods or processes. Without such implementation, an invention, modification or improvement cannot be considered an innovation. He noted that innovation must be distinguished from invention since innovation is a social activity or "function" carried out inside the economic field and with a business objective, whereas inventions can be carried out anywhere and without commercial intent (Schumpeter, 1934). Thus, for Schumpeter, innovation is the process through which new ideas are generated and put into commercial practice. Already in Schumpeter's definition of innovation, there is a key characteristic: innovation is a process with distinct phases: design, implementation, and commercialization. The second essential characteristic of innovation is that it provides added value to the industry/organization that introduces it to the market. Consequently, innovation is closely related to value creation, and it is reasonable to say that innovation has become the key strategy for any company to survive and expand in today's highly competitive and dynamic global market (Lee et al., 2012).

It is difficult to overestimate the importance of the innovation process since it is widely recognized as the primary driver of sustainable economic growth. As stated by Schumpeter (1934, p. 82-83) "The fundamental impulse that sets and keeps the capitalist engine in motion comes from the new consumers' goods, the new methods of production or transportation, the new markets, the new forces of industrial organisation that capitalist enterprise creates." "This is also represented in the well-established OECD policy knowledge, which categorises world economies into three stages: from a pre-industrial, critical basis in natural resources to cheap labour in industrial mass production to the innovation-based stage" (Katzy, 2005 cited in Schuurman, 2015, 25-26).

Two prominent paradigms offer contrasting perspectives on the post-development phase of innovation: the diffusion of innovations and the social shaping of innovation theories.

The most well-established generalisations of adoption diffusion theory are as follows (Rogers, 2003):

- Innovations have certain characteristics that ultimately determine the rate and patterns of adoption.
- Some potential adopters are more innovative than others, and this can be determined based on their individual characteristics.
- The adoption decision is conceptualised as a series of stages.
- Certain individuals' behaviours can impact the adoption decisions of others.
- The diffusion curve is S-shaped due to a slow start, followed by a rapid increase once the "tipping point" is achieved, and then saturation at a specific market level, resulting in a decline in growth.

During the 1980s objections such as the technological deterministic character of this paradigm ('technology shapes society') and the lack of attention to the eventual usage of innovation have resulted in the development of a second line of research: the so-called "social shaping of technology". It relates to how the use of innovations in households is socially negotiated, with a focus on the technological content and innovation processes. We can locate the "domestication" study tradition within this framework. Domestication is the study of the cultural, social, and technical networks of the everyday life of households.

Four stages characterise the concept:

- appropriation: when a technology leaves the world of commodities, it is appropriated. Then it can be taken by an individual or a household and owned. From this perspective, appropriation stands for the whole process of consumption as well as for that moment at which an object crosses the threshold between formal and moral economics (Miller, 1988, cited in (Schuurman, 2015);

- objectification: this is expressed in usage but also in psychological dispositions of objects in the spatial environment of the home;
- incorporation: how objects, especially technologies are used;
- conversion: defines the relationship between the household and the outside world. Technologies may pass the household confines and claim themselves as members of the “wider society”.

As is the case with most dichotomous academic disputes, scholars argued that the quantitative, technologically deterministic “diffusion of innovations” and the qualitative, socially deterministic “domestication” can be viewed as complementing each other. In place of technological determinism and social shaping, the “mutual shaping” or “interactionism” approach emerged in the late 1990s as a dynamic middle ground between the two linearly deterministic predecessors (Schuurman, 2015, p. 30). This approach enabled the combination of the adoption diffusion and use diffusion perspectives, as the “diffusion of innovations” examines the adoption process and “domestication” investigates what occurs after adoption. This mutual shaping refers to the influence of technology on society, as well as the influence of society on technology. The supposed connection between design (pre-launch) and domestication (post-launch), as well as the mutual influence of both processes, emphasised the need for pre-launch user research and user involvement, with a focus on the broader societal implications of innovation.

Innovation is a process with a substantial subjective component, to summarise. Indeed, we acknowledge that there is a social influence on innovation and that innovation may include modifications or enhancements beyond product innovation. In addition, this subjective dimension focuses on the end-user who experiences or consumes the innovation and, by doing so or not, has a stake in the innovation's ultimate success. By tying innovation to some form of acceptance or market success, the role of the innovation's eventual end-user is subsequently raised.

1.2 The Closed Innovation Model

Innovation is not a single act or action, but rather a process, or even a series of processes, as we have previously stated. Furthermore, not all actions or inventions result in innovation. To

achieve (successful) innovation, therefore, orchestration and management of these processes are necessary (Schumpeter, 1934). Thus, the discipline of managing innovation processes is known as innovation management. The objective of innovation management is to enable the organisation to respond to an external or internal opportunity or need by introducing new ideas, processes, or products through its creative efforts (Kelly & Kranzberg, 1978). The Closed Innovation management model dominated the 20th century; its central premise was that companies experienced significant economies of scale when integrating all R&D efforts within the company. According to Chesbrough (2003, p.36), this closed innovation paradigm leads to a virtuous circle in which increased investment in R&D leads to fundamental technology breakthroughs and to new products and features, which in turn lead to increased sales and profits via existing business models, which in turn enables an organisation to increase its investment in R&D. Still, the virtuous cycle had side effects:

- Arrow (1962, cited in Schuurman, 2015, p. 59) underlines that those economic spillovers. are a byproduct of investing in research and development because it is impossible to predict the outcome of the research. This indicates that research and development produce "excess" knowledge that does not result in fundamental breakthroughs or new products.
- Teece (1986, cited in Schuurman, 2015, p. 59) stresses that “research needs to be appropriated in order to come to successful innovation”. He demonstrated that the winners of innovative ideas are not necessarily the original inventors but can also be companies that control distribution and consumer service, for instance. This already provides some evidence against the virtuous circle of closed innovation. In his later work, he introduced the concept of dynamic capabilities, which he defines as the capacity of firms or organisations to respond to rapidly changing environments by integrating, constructing, or reconfiguring internal and external competencies. This concept is coupled with the concept of an organization's absorptive capacity, or the capacity to recognise the value of new knowledge, appropriate it, and apply it for commercial purposes.

Nonetheless, internal R&D served as a valuable strategic advantage, acting as a substantial entry barrier for competitors in various markets. Only prominent corporations like DuPont, IBM, and AT&T could effectively compete by carrying out extensive research and development within their respective industries, subsequently reaping the majority of profits.

To challenge these industry giants, competitors needed to invest considerable sums to establish their own research facilities. However, by the close of the 20th century, the established industrial leaders faced remarkably fierce competition from numerous emerging players. Interestingly, these newcomers diverged from traditional norms by relying less on independent basic research and instead introducing new ideas to the market using alternative approaches.

Chesbrough (2003) illustrates this transformation using Lucent Technologies and Cisco Systems as an example. Lucent inherited a significant portion of Bell Laboratories after the AT&T breakup, which was a pinnacle of industrial research in the 20th century. This advantage should have given Lucent a decisive edge in the telecommunications equipment market. Yet, the outcome was not as anticipated. Despite lacking an equivalent to Bell Labs' extensive internal R&D capabilities, Cisco Systems consistently outperformed Lucent and occasionally even beat it to market. This prompts the question: What led to this outcome?

While Lucent and Cisco competed directly in the same industry, their innovation strategies diverged. Lucent allocated substantial resources to delve into new materials, cutting-edge components, and systems, seeking groundbreaking discoveries that would fuel future product and service development. On the other hand, Cisco pursued a notably distinct approach to innovation leadership. The company obtained the necessary technology externally, primarily through partnerships with or investments in promising startups. Cisco managed to keep pace with the R&D output of one of the world's premier industrial R&D organizations without conducting a substantial amount of its own research.

The question then arises as to why internal R&D is no longer a strategic asset. The answer lies in a fundamental shift in how enterprises generate and business new ideas. For a long time, the logic of closed innovation was implicitly regarded as self-evident as the "right way," and actually the model worked and worked well for a long time. At the end of the twentieth century, however, a number of factors combined to undermine the foundations of closed innovation, and the innovation cycle was broken.

1.3 The Open Innovation Model

All of the evolutions discussed in this subchapter are premised on the awareness of the distributed nature of innovation. The origins of this phenomenon can be traced back to the 1940s when Friedrich von Hayek (1945) argued that knowledge is unevenly distributed in

society. Applying this to innovation development requires tapping into various types of knowledge from various sources, which implies a fundamental shift in innovation management, as, along with internal firms' assets, external capabilities have to be developed and managed. The distributed nature of innovation implies that the *locus* where knowledge is created (invention or research) does not always correspond to the *locus* of innovation (in terms of applying the idea and transforming it into an innovation); furthermore, innovation and commercialisation (product development or exploitation of the innovation) do not need to be located in the same *locus*, as already pointed out by Teece as one of the side effects of the Closed Innovation model. This phenomenon is known as "distributed innovation," or the fact that leveraging multiple external sources of knowledge when innovating yields better outcomes (Lakhani & Panetta, 2007). Since the turn of the century, firms' most valuable resource has been knowledge (Gassmann, 2006), and external sources of knowledge and innovation have become increasingly significant.

Awareness of the distributed nature of knowledge and other "erosion factors", including a dramatic increase in the number and mobility of knowledge workers, as well as an increase in the availability of private venture capital and shorter product life cycles, led to cracks in the foundations of the virtuous cycle of Closed Innovation model (Chesbrough, 2003).

According to Schuurman (2015), there are environmental factors at which adapting is becoming more and more a prerequisite for companies to survive, these three environmental factors influence the success of innovation:

- the speed at which innovations are introduced, which has increased;
- the intensity of competition, which has increased too in some industries due to unexpected competitors;
- the increased availability and accessibility of information.

These environmental factors are coupled with the increasing relevance and new opportunities of information and communications technology (ICT).

1. ICT has been a main driver in spreading knowledge worldwide among a variety of different actors as these technologies have dissolved a lot of time- and place-based bonds;

2. these factors have in turn intensified competition by fostering convergence and dissolving bonds between previously separate markets which causes the shortening of innovation life cycles;
3. ICT has revolutionised and facilitated knowledge transfer and increased companies' capacity for innovation.
4. The role of network externalities, which means that the value of adoption increases with each additional adopter, is another reason why ICTs are a "special case" when studying the diffusion of innovations (Katz & Shapiro, 1986).

All the processes and elements discussed led Chesbrough to define a new innovation paradigm in 2003: the Open Innovation (OI) model.

The first premise of OI is that, from the perspective of a single company, opening the firm's internal innovation process generates added value. OI is a non-linear innovation process characterised by increased collaboration between internal R&D departments and the outside world, with companies reaping the synergies associated with this collaboration.

In the new model of OI, the company commercializes both its own ideas as well as innovations from other firms and seeks to bring its own innovations to market by deploying channels outside of its current business. Note that the boundary between the organisation and its surrounding environment is permeable, allowing knowledge to move between the two with greater ease (Chesbrough, 2003).

Figure 1- Open Innovation funnel

(Chesbrough, 2003)

Three core OI processes were identified as a result of research into these knowledge transfers:

1. The outside-in process: enriching the company's knowledge base by integrating customers and suppliers, and external knowledge sourcing (or exploration). This implies purposive knowledge inflows;
2. The inside-out process: generating profits by bringing ideas to market, selling intellectual property, and expanding technology by transferring ideas to the external environment. This implies purposive outflows of knowledge;
3. Coupled process: which implies combined knowledge inflows and outflows between actors in the innovation process (Chesbrough & Bogers, 2013). Enkel et al., (2009) compare the coupled process to co-creation with complementary partners who engage in simultaneous outside-in and inside-out processes via alliances, cooperations, and/or joint ventures.

This process perspective on OI sheds a different light on the literature on R&D spillovers, in which these knowledge leaks or spillovers were viewed as threats to the innovation process: Arrow (1962, cited in Schuurman, 2015, p. 59) argues that spillovers are a byproduct of investing in R&D because the outcome of the research cannot be predicted, as already underlined. This implies that R&D generates "excess" knowledge that does not lead to fundamental breakthroughs or new products. Moreover, as we know, Teece (1986, cited in Schuurman, 2015, p. 59) argues that research must be appropriated for innovation to be successful. He demonstrated that the winners of innovative ideas are not necessarily the original inventors but can also be companies that control distribution and consumer service, for instance. In this way introduces somehow the idea of different *loci* of innovation. According to Chesbrough and Bogers (2013), the OI concept is aimed at handling the mechanisms and characteristics of such spillovers on purpose. Furthermore, these spillovers are regarded as an integral component of the OI strategy of a business or organisation.

Lichtenthaler (2011) states that in the light of the three OI processes, OI networks demand three corresponding firm capabilities:

- absorptive capacity, or the ability to deal with knowledge exploration;
- connective or the ability to deal with knowledge retention;

- desorptive capacity or the ability to deal with knowledge exploitation.

He also argues that these OI networks capabilities need to be balanced with internal firm capabilities that are also linked to the three OI processes, as internal and external processes are often complementary at the organisational level:

- inventive capacity;
- transformative capacity;
- innovative capacity.

		Knowledge exploration	Knowledge retention	Knowledge exploitation
Internal	<i>Organizational level</i>	Inventive capacity	Transformative capacity	Innovative capacity
	<i>Project level</i>	Make decision	Integrate decision	Keep decision
	<i>Individual level</i>	Not-invented-here attitude	Not-connected-here attitude	Not-sold-here attitude
External	<i>Organizational level</i>	Absorptive capacity	Connective capacity	Desorptive capacity
	<i>Project level</i>	Buy decision	Relate decision	Sell decision
	<i>Individual level</i>	Buy-in attitude	Relate-out attitude	Sell-out attitude

Table 1 - Open Innovation processes and related company capabilities

(Schuurman, 2015, p.71)

Regarding the 'coupled process,' which is absent from Lichtenthaler's framework, Bogers (2011) identifies the following characteristics as having a significant impact on the nature and outcome of the collaboration: experience of and with partners, university involvement, number of partners, partners size, and duration.

1.3.1 Open Innovation and Living Labs

The majority of the OI concepts and literature discussed take a single company or the process of knowledge exchange between companies as the unit of analysis. However, these interactions may also occur within a larger network or constellation of actors engaged in OI.

Living Labs are comprised of multiple actors engaged in innovation projects involving knowledge transfers and collaborative activities (such as co-creation), therefore they require a more encompassing perspective that is able to analyse and describe these networked structures and activities. Thus, we turn to the literature on systemic innovation, (open) innovation networks and systemic instruments for concepts and frameworks to facilitate this network view on Living Labs. The first concept “innovation systems” operates on a more "macro" scale than innovation networks. Despite the lack of a unified definition, the concept of the innovation system recognises the importance of technology and information transfers between individuals, businesses, organisations, and institutions in the innovation process (Schuurman, 2015, p. 73). According to Wieczorek and Hekkert (2012, p.76), an innovation system “comprises all the parts and aspects of an economic structure and the institutional set-up affecting learning, searching and exploring: the production, marketing and finance system.”

Following the broad definition of innovation systems, innovation networks can be viewed as a component of these systems. They can be defined as purposefully established connections between the demand side (intermediate and end-users of innovation) and the supply side (producers of knowledge and technologies) of the knowledge infrastructure, as well as with other relevant actors from within the innovation system.

Klerkx and Aarts (2013, cited in Schuurman, 2015, p.74) provide an overview of the three primary challenges and paradoxes associated with OI networks. First, they must strike a balance between new and established relationships. Second, the ways in which network actors interact must consider their divergent perspectives on the nature and structure of the cooperation. Third, formal and informal relationships between network participants must be balanced. Actors in the network need to manage the paradox that they must strengthen their position in the network to reap the benefits, but that total control of the network by a single company may be counterproductive because it undermines the informal foundation of network cooperation.

These obstacles can be overcome through the network orchestration process. The literature on such orchestration identifies three fundamental elements:

- demand articulation;
- innovation network structure;

- innovation process management.

This resulted in the creation of systemic instruments designed to address problems such as an innovation intermediary, a visible hand that coordinates innovation processes in open networks. Within this framework, Living Labs are considered as process coordinating innovation intermediaries for "(1) closing the pre-commercial gap by manifesting initial demand for products and services, and (2) orchestrating the actions of disparate actors in order to gain critical mass for the creation of a product or service" (Almirall & Wareham, 2011, p. 101). Thus, Living Labs can be viewed as OI networks that serve as systemic instruments and innovation intermediaries to overcome innovation barriers for the network's actors.

In conclusion, in the OI paradigm, innovation processes are essentially focused on the exchange of relevant knowledge between actors. This also supports the notion that innovation is a process, as knowledge creation, innovation, and commercialization are distinguished. The exchanges can take three different forms: exploitation (also referred to as inside-out), exploration (also referred to as outside-in), and retention (the storage and/or re-use of knowledge over time). Each of the three processes is associated with an internal and external organisational capability: inventive and absorptive capacity, innovative and desruptive capacity, and transformative and connective capacity.

In OI Systems, we view an innovation network as a purposeful connection between all of the relevant innovation system actors. Such a network must be managed by an innovation intermediary. Living Labs can be seen as such intermediaries.

1.4 The User Innovation Paradigm

The distributed nature of knowledge in society is central not only to the OI model, but also to the User Innovation paradigm, according to Bogers and West (2012). Both make sense of distributed innovation phenomena but from fundamentally different perspectives. Whereas OI looks at this from a firm's perspective, attempting to determine how a single firm can derive the greatest benefit from these principles, User Innovation begins with the end-users and their needs and examines how innovation can best meet these needs. We agree with Schuurman (2015) who views User Innovation as a form of distributed innovation that recognises the user as a source of innovation. This makes the User Innovation model perfectly compatible with the

OI literature: in both paradigms, the innovation process is inherently opened beyond the traditional closed, in-house firm innovation process.

However, the initial main question of User Innovation researchers was fundamentally different: “Under which circumstances do users start innovating themselves?” This was later expanded to include the question, “Which users can be involved in innovation processes and how?”.

Three distinct approaches to user involvement can be distinguished. The first strategy is User Innovation with and by Lead Users. Lead Users can be considered the “Holy Grail” of user engagement because, by definition, they provide access to new market needs that will become widespread. However, the most significant issue was that identifying Lead Users resembled searching for needles in a haystack. To move beyond descriptive Lead User papers, research was conducted into the nature and characteristics of these Lead Users as well as identification methods. This eventually led to the second strategy, in which User Innovation research examined a broader range of users who were deemed capable of actively participating in new product development (NPD). Recognizing that users have varying levels of expertise and knowledge, the researchers found out that businesses must match the NPD stage, user role, and user type for each new innovation project to ensure fruitful co-creation (Jespersen, 2008). Recently, the scope of User Innovation and user involvement has expanded even further, as research has begun to examine the possibilities and methodologies for ‘ordinary’ user participation in NPD (Kristensson et al., 2008).

1.4.1 The roots of User innovation

The roots of User Innovation can be traced back to the 1970s. In terms of innovation management, this period was characterised by the shift from a “market pull” paradigm, where an innovation process began by generating user needs, to a coupled model, attempting to integrate both “technology push” and “market pull” (Schuurman, 2015). During his early research on innovation, von Hippel (1986) noticed that regular market research, used for need detection when innovating within the “market pull” paradigm, usually fosters general needs that are common in the marketplace. This resulted in a wave of ‘incrementalism’ or innovations that consisted primarily of minor modifications or adjustments to existing products or services. In lieu of conventional market research, he advocated for new tools that could generate novel and innovative input and trends, which would lead to breakthrough, ground-breaking innovation (von Hippel, 1976). Important to his work is the distinction von Hippel makes

between the "user" and "manufacturer" of an innovation, where the former uses an innovation but does not produce it for sale, and the latter produces an innovation for sale but does not use it. In his study on scientific instruments, he found that for both major and minor innovations in this field, it was the user, not the manufacturer, who identified the need, solved the problem through invention, built a prototype and demonstrated the prototype's value through use (von Hippel, 1976). In other words, the *locus* of almost the entire innovation process within the domain of scientific instruments is situated with the user, whereas only "commercial diffusion" is carried out by the manufacturer. In other sectors and instances, von Hippel discovered different patterns regarding the *locus* of innovation. Based on the shifting *locus* of innovation in the various stages of the innovation process, he proposed three innovation patterns: a user-dominant pattern, a commercializer-dominant pattern, and a material supplier-dominant pattern.

Von Hippel not only witnessed the distributed nature of innovation near the end of the 1970s but in his observations we can detect the foundations of the OI paradigm, as he acknowledged that the firm opened up its innovation process to external inputs to benefit from them and that an innovation generated by one firm (the material supplier) could be externally commercialised by another firm (the manufacturer). In addition, he acknowledged the existence of multiple "*loci* of innovation" which is the basis of the OI model.

As a counterbalance to the dominant manufacturer active paradigm (MAP), in which the manufacturer generates all innovation by him/her-self, Von Hippel introduced the customer active paradigm (CAP), which implied that the user could take the initiative at various stages of the innovation process under certain circumstances. Looking deeper into the nature and traits of these "innovating users", he introduced the "Lead User"-concept (von Hippel, 1986). Lead Users of a new or enhanced product, process, or service exhibit two primary characteristics: a) Lead Users face needs months or years before they become common in a market, and b) Lead Users expect significant benefits from obtaining a solution to these needs. Lead Users are users from the leading edge of the target market or users from markets with more extreme forms of similar problems. Lead Users have real-world experience with novel product or process concepts (von Hippel, 1986), allowing them to serve as a "need-forecasting laboratory" (Schoorman, 2015, p 93). Additionally, Lead Users are viewed as sources of innovative solutions (von Hippel, 2005). It is also argued that being a Lead User is relative to the trend or innovation domain that is being considered, meaning that an individual who is a Lead User in

one field is not required to be a lead user in a completely different or even adjacent field (von Hippel, 1986). This indicates that von Hippel considers Lead Users capable of generating information regarding both needs and solutions. In later works, von Hippel linked Lead Users to the notion of “sticky information” which suggests that user needs can be latent and therefore difficult to communicate to the manufacturer (von Hippel, 1994). When a company successfully integrates Lead Users into its innovation processes, it may be able to overcome this information stickiness and address its own functional rigidity.

1.4.2 Redefining Lead Users: Expanding User Roles in Innovation Processes

Attempts have been made in the literature on Lead Users to outline a method for involving Lead Users in innovation processes. Four basic steps can be identified (Schuurman, 2015):

- the identification of a significant market or technical trend;
- the identification of Lead Users for the trend identified in step one;
- the development and testing of innovation based on solution data from Lead Users (this third step is cyclical and iterative in nature);
- the testing of the innovation on the general market.

For this process to be effective, Lead Users must possess specific characteristics, such as unmet needs and the potential for substantial benefit once these needs are met. Urban and von Hippel (1988) recommend using three proxies when searching for a high expected benefit from addressing a need, the second Lead User indicator after being ahead of a market trend. They include:

1. evidence of user product modification or development (users who have innovated);
2. user dissatisfaction with existing products or solutions and
3. speed of innovation adoption.

In the other hand, Lüthje (2004) attributes the ability of Lead Users to be effective contributors to the innovation process to two major characteristics: adequate technological expertise and

superior knowledge of the user domain ('use experience'). The first characteristic can be viewed as a prerequisite for the innovating user-criterion, as the ability to innovate or modify requires a certain level of technological expertise, whereas the second characteristic relates to the use diffusion paradigm, as it suggests that Lead Users have a high intensity of use.

The literature on Lead Users has evolved as authors have shifted away from the 'classical' definition of a Lead User to focus more on other characteristics and screening methods. This can also be attributed to the fact that these Lead User methodologies appeared to be both expensive and time-consuming.

Researchers initiated an exploration into the nature of user engagement and the alignment of user categories with different phases of NPD. This investigation emerged as a response to the limited attention given to these aspects within the existing literature on Lead Users. In a sense, this trajectory of User Innovation research still builds upon the "market pull" paradigm, since it emphasizes the necessity of precisely identifying and addressing user needs, which are subject to change throughout the innovation process (Schuurman, 2015).

The recognition that user needs are not static necessitates continuous user involvement beyond Voice of the Customer techniques, not only at the outset of an innovation trajectory but throughout its development and refinement. This shift has prompted User Innovation researchers to focus on more tangible user characteristics, coupled with exploring strategies to engage users at various stages of the NPD process, with different levels of involvement.

However, when referring to user roles and characteristics during the NPD process, the NPD process is conceptualised as a very linear sequence of ideation, research and development, testing, and commercialization. In addition, it is unclear how to recruit these users, how to keep them motivated, and how this involvement should be structured throughout the various NPD phases. Furthermore, and despite the increasingly complex conceptualizations of user characteristics, our initial Lead User remained the ideal user type to be involved with. This search for more actionable user types to be involved has the advantage of highlighting the fact that the level of user involvement can vary depending on the desired outcome and contribution and that different user types can make different contributions.

A significant breakthrough in the research field was introduced by Magnusson (2009, cited in Schuurman, 2015, p. 103) who, asserts that too much expertise and knowledge may impede the development of novel, original, and creative knowledge, pleading for the inclusion of end users

who do not exhibit Lead User-characteristics. The involved users are not Lead Users, as previously defined, however, they cannot be classified as "ordinary users" either, as they appear to exhibit certain innovation-related characteristics, such as dissatisfaction with the current product offering (defectors) or personality-related traits such as creativity or enthusiasm. Instead of carefully selecting these users, it is assumed that the "right" type of "ordinary user" is attained through self-selection during the user involvement process.

The evolution of Lead User methodologies highlights the dynamic nature of user involvement in innovation processes. While early approaches focused on identifying Lead Users with specific characteristics, more recent research has expanded the scope to include a broader range of user types. This shift reflects a growing recognition that innovation can benefit from the diverse perspectives of users with varying levels of expertise and engagement. By embracing a more flexible and inclusive approach, companies can better address evolving user needs and foster more creative, impactful innovations.

1.4.3 Co-Design with Users: The Evolution of User Participation in Innovation

In 2009, Piller and Ihl (cited in Schuurman, 2015) advocated for a collaborative mode of user participation, which they refer to as "design by users" or OI with customers. It relies on co-design and allows the innovation focus to shift between users/customers and producers. Initially, it was believed that co-design was only suitable for users with specific Lead-User or other characteristics; however, it has recently been suggested that ordinary users can also contribute to radical innovation (Schuurman, 2015).

The concept of co-design emerged from the Scandinavian Cooperative Design tradition, which was later adapted into American Participatory Design. The origins of cooperative design trace back to the 1970s when various research projects across Scandinavia focused on involving users in system development processes. These early initiatives, driven by influential labour unions, concentrated on engaging employees in designing IT applications for their workplaces. Collaboration between the organization's workers and researchers was integral to these efforts. This collaborative approach allowed researchers to gather data while workers influenced the implementation of IT systems in their daily routines, highlighting the reciprocal nature of value co-creation. Fowles (2000) refers to this transformation from a "symmetry of ignorance"

(where designers and users misunderstand each other) to a complementary "symmetry of knowledge" achieved through participation and learning symmetries. Within these projects, the cooperative design methodology stemmed from participants' personal experiences, underscoring the significance of shared resources and knowledge accumulation in Cooperative Design.

In their 1991 book 'Design at Work: Cooperative Design of Computer Systems,' Greenbaum & Kyng shed light on the evolution from Scandinavian Cooperative Design to north American Participatory Design (PD), based on their own experiences. The transition towards PD began in 1986 when Joan Greenbaum visited Denmark and started exchanging insights about his experiences in the United States. This led to the expansion and enrichment of the original principles of Cooperative Design with ideas from various fields, culminating in the establishment of PD as a collection of theories, practices, and studies centred around involving end users as active participants in creating software, hardware, and computer-based activities (Schuurman, 2015). The field of PD is extremely diverse, multi- and inter-disciplinary by nature, and constructed from localised experiences in diverse national and cultural contexts (J. Gregory, 2003).

Because we began using technology not only at work, but also at home, in school, and even while "on the move" in recent years, it has been a significant challenge for PD to adjust to the fact that much technology development no longer occurs as the design of isolated systems in well-defined work communities. Consequently, the so-called User-Centred Design (UCD) approach has gained a great deal of popularity. UCD is a multi-stage problem-solving process that requires designers not only to analyse and anticipate how users are likely to use a product but also to test the validity of their hypotheses regarding user behaviour in real-world tests with actual users. Focus on users and tasks, empirical measurement of product usage in field trials, and iterative design are the three guiding principles of User-Centred Design (Gould & Lewis, 1985).

In conclusion, the progression from Lead User innovation to broader participatory design paradigm marks a significant shift in how user involvement is approached within innovation processes. Initially centered on specialized users with unique insights, contemporary frameworks now emphasize the value of collaboration across diverse user groups. The Scandinavian Cooperative Design tradition, which laid the foundation for Participatory Design, underscores the importance of integrating user expertise into the development process,

fostering a reciprocal exchange of knowledge. As technological advancements permeate all aspects of life, approaches like User-Centered Design have evolved to ensure that innovation remains deeply aligned with user needs, resulting in more effective and human-centric outcomes.

1.5 Linking Open and User Innovation: Co-creation

As already underlined, Open Innovation and User Innovation are models for understanding the distributed nature of innovation in our society. We are aware that at the core of OI processes is the recognition of the presence of multiple *loci* of innovation, and therefore that opening the firm's innovation processes to external actors generates added value for the firm. According to Schuurman (2015) User Innovation is a form of distributed innovation that recognises the user as a source of innovation. This makes the User Innovation paradigm perfectly compatible with the OI model, as the user can be viewed as an external source of innovation by a company. In OI the firm opens its boundaries for external ideas or knowledge to flow in, or for internal assets to flow out of the company to be externally commercialized or exploited, whereas User Innovation emphasizes 'free revealing' and the user interest in finding a solution to their need and 'using' the innovation. Exactly these fundamentally different perspectives are responsible for the 'gap' between the two paradigms, although they seem to be part of larger research domains and contemporary phenomenon: the distributed nature of knowledge (Schuurman, 2015). Co-creation can be seen as the bridge between the two paradigms (Piller & West, 2014; Schuurman, 2015).

According to Mastelic (2019, p. 15), "the notion of value co-creation is [...] the outcome of the co-design process". The objective of a company's decision to open its R&D department to the outside world (OI) and to implement a co-design process with its users (User Innovation) is to co-create value. Co-design, therefore, refers to the application of collective creativity throughout the whole design process, the result of the co-design process is the co-creation of value.

The development of co-design strategies with users or external stakeholders and the co-creation of value has become increasingly crucial for every company or organisation, as customers are increasingly becoming change agents of the firm as well as the actual owners of organisations' primary means of production, namely knowledge (Ramaswamy & Guillard, 2010). On the other hand, customers are also demanding greater levels of personalization in their

consumption experiences, thereby placing businesses under a growing amount of pressure to co-create value with them. Why?

- A combination of forethought and intuition. Our understanding of invention is evolving. According to social scientist Nigel Thrift, (cited in Ramaswamy & Gouillart, 2010) the change is exemplified by three trends: (1) the deployment of forethought (a type of tacit knowledge. Businesses are increasingly valuing intuition or implicit thought as a source of expertise); (2) the co-creation of products with consumers; (3) the creation of an environment that fosters innovation.
- Consumers' collective intelligence. Concurrently, experience-based consumer knowledge is increasingly regarded as a valuable asset. According to this perspective, co-creation between firms and customers, as well as production and consumption, is about effectively leveraging the collective intelligence of consumers.
- Co-creation of value is predominant. The notion of 'co-creation of value' has become a prevalent concept. It occurs when consumers interact with companies or products and, as a result, actively shape their experience and, ultimately, their perception of value.

Co-creation involves both a profound democratization and decentralization of value creation.

The core principle underlying the transformation of enterprises toward co-creation is this: engaging people to create valuable experiences together enhancing network economics. The co-creation paradigm is characterised by four components:

- Experience mindset;
- Context of interactions;
- Engagement platforms;
- Network relationships.

Put together these four components liberate four powers of co-creation: increased capital and return to the firm, valuable experience for the customers and reduced risks and costs for both the firm and the customer (Ramaswamy & Gouillart, 2010).

Consider Nike as an example of a co-creative enterprise in action and the power of value co-creation. Nike launched Nike+ in 2006 in partnership with Apple to engage runners and the running community at large on a deeper level. Nike+ consisted of a smart sensor on the shoe that can communicate with the iPod and iPhone's built-in wireless receiver. As you run while listening to music, the sensor electronically records the time and distance of your run, keeping track of any records you set. A voice-over recording offers congratulations and encouragement when a new record is set. You can upload data from your run to the Nike+ website, chart it, analyse it, and share it with other participants. However, Nike+ transcends a collection of devices and websites: the running experience is the result of the runner's interactions with Nike+. There are multiple ways a runner can interact with this platform.

- The runner can automatically plot distance, time, pace, and calories burned using the tracking function. Nike+ also provides an overview of any data set over time, allowing users to determine whether they are making progress.
- In Nike+, conversing and exchanging experiences with other runners. The runner can issue challenges to other runners, as well as share his/her Running Playlists and courses.
- Runners can now map and share their runs through a partnership between Nike and Google. Each time they establish a new course, Google Maps will display it.
- The runner can also download local data to determine the prevalent running speed in the area.
- Runners can join local Like Running Clubs through Nike+. There, they will be able to participate in running clinics and runner incentive programmes.
- Runners can also participate in virtual training with a running coach or interact with running stars and have a private conversation. They can participate in a variety of blog and discussion board interactions with the running community at large.

For the runner, value is a function of the running experience. This is produced in part by the user and in part by Nike+, the engagement platform. Consequently, the runner and Nike+ co-create the running experience.

The Nike+ system enables the generation of profound knowledge and insights about the running experience and provides Nike with access to an extraordinary amount of real-time data.

Thus, Nike now has a live laboratory in which it continuously learns and generates insights from data regarding customers' running mileage and musical preferences. Nike+ is an interactive platform that fosters the ongoing expansion of Nike offerings and enables Nike to:

- learn directly from the behaviour of its customers;
- generate new ideas rapidly;
- experiment with new offerings quickly;
- get direct input from customers on their running preferences;
- build deeper relationships and trust with the community;
- generate stickier brand collateral.

These advantages to the enterprise are referred to as strategic capital: Nike has captured 57% of the \$3.6 billion US running shoe market by the end of 2007, up from 47% in 2006. Nike's share of the U.S. running shoe market increased to 61% by mid-2009 (Ramaswamy & Gouillart, 2010).

Moreover, Nike+ has reduced dangers and expenses for Nike, reducing conventional marketing costs; sharing the risk of product/service development with partners like Apple through co-investment and participation. It can now test major investments through its engagement platform, thereby mitigating the risk of capital investment through enlightened experimentation.

On the customer side, the benefits emphasise the actual human experience of running, as opposed to the conventional product-centric view of value. Former Nike's global director of consumer connections, Stefan Olander, stated that "in the past, the product was the end point of the consumer experience. Now it is the starting point." (Gregory, 2007). Nike+ expands value as a result of new types of valuable individual experiences.

To conclude, Nike+ increases enterprise returns and strategic capital. It reduces risks and expenses for the business. It allows individuals to acquire new, valuable experiences and reduces the risks and expenses for them. Therefore, Nike+ has mastered the four essential co-creation powers. The initiative has been so successful that the engagement platform is evolving over time, adapting itself to the new technologies' development. The website has become the

Nike Run Club app for iOS, it can be directly linked to the Apple Watch, and it has been expanded to include a Nike Training Club, through which individuals can train at home with the leading experts of the Nike community, as well as engaging with other trainees.

In essence, co-creation revolves around the process of generating significant and fulfilling experiences. It functions as a continuous cycle, serving as both the method and the objective. Neurologists emphasize that meaningful interactions among individuals facilitate accelerated learning and improved retention of knowledge. Recognizing the utmost importance of individuals and their human experiences as the foundation of value creation is the key transformation that leaders need to embrace (Ramaswamy & Gouillart, 2010).

In our conceptual model that positioned Living Labs in relation to Open and User Innovation, we agree with Piller & West (2014) and Schuurman (2015) in viewing the co-creation process between users and businesses as the potential "bridge" between Open and User Innovation. Therefore, as co-creation is regarded as the central tenet of Living Labs, following Schurman, we see the study of Living Lab activities as a potential means to overcome this gap.

2. Living Labs

2.1 History

In the final three decades of the 20th century, three noteworthy phenomena emerged as precursors to the contemporary living lab movement. These antecedents laid the foundation for the living labs we recognize today: the “cooperative design movement”, the European social experiments with information technology, and the advent of “digital city” initiatives.

2.1.1 Cooperative Design

The tradition of cooperative design traces its roots back to the 1970s when research projects across Scandinavia explored the active involvement of users in systems development. Unlike traditional approaches that merely observed users, cooperative design pioneered a paradigm shift by granting users equal footing with designers and researchers throughout the development and implementation of information technology (IT) artefacts. This collaborative tradition later evolved, often sharing a focus on the "social shaping of technology." It aimed to steer and optimise innovations based on user preferences, sometimes adopting a "sociodeterministic" view of innovation. The subsequent North American Participatory Design movement drew inspiration from these Scandinavian initiatives, leading to the emergence of the user-centred design (UCD) approach. This UCD approach emphasised early user involvement, empirical product measurement in field trials, and iterative design. Within the Cooperative Design tradition (See 1.4.3 Co-Design with Users: The Evolution of User Participation in Innovation), two fundamental elements that resonate with living labs today were born: the user-centric perspective and real-life context. A key distinction is that the real-life setting is mostly utilised to examine present behaviours and that these activities were carried out specifically in the framework of IT for work (Schuurman, 2015).

2.1.2 Social Experiments

In the 1980s, Europe witnessed the emergence of social experiments with information technology (IT), which served as a foundational precursor to the concept of living labs. These experiments, grounded in psychological research, ventured beyond the confines of traditional laboratory environments to embrace the complexities of real-world settings. They eschewed

rigid procedural frameworks in favour of more flexible, prolonged interventions aimed at evaluating comprehensive intervention strategies rather than isolated, theoretically driven constructs (Ballon & Schuurman, 2015). Central to these experiments was the active participation of users, predicated on the belief that the diffusion of IT technologies hinged on a reciprocal learning process between suppliers and users, culminating in their mutual adoption. This interaction not only yielded insights for the creation of novel technological solutions but also fostered “social inventions” by modifying user behaviour in response to these technological advancements. This period marked a departure from the previously dominant “social shaping” perspective, associated with the cooperative design methods of the 1970s, towards a 'mutual shaping' approach to IT development. The adoption of social experiments in ICT, particularly under the European Commission's FAST program, was driven by three evaluative objectives: fostering socially beneficial IT use, creating high-quality information and communication systems, and shaping future technological and societal trajectories through innovative IT products and societal learning (Qvortrup, 1987, as cited in Schuurman, 2015).

Two pivotal attributes that would later define living labs emerge from European social experiments: the emphasis on real-life testing environments and multi-stakeholder participation as national and local public institutions, national and local private organizations, and end-users were involved in the process. The role of the end-user was also considered in these initiatives, however, the exact nature of this user involvement remained open to interpretation; users might be mere testers or respondents, or they might engage as co-creators or even innovators in their own right (Ballon & Schuurman, 2015). This ambiguity reflects the evolving understanding of user roles within the broader context of innovation processes in Europe.

2.1.3 Digital City Initiatives

In the 1990s, the concept of the “digital city” gained prominence in Europe and beyond. These initiatives encompassed various digital efforts by cities, primarily centred on digital city representations and providing internet access to citizens. Central to the discourse surrounding these initial digital city initiatives were the network infrastructure and platforms designed to disseminate vast quantities of digital information, imbuing the concept with a distinctly technology-deterministic undertone. However, over the course of the 1990s, the digital city concept underwent a transformation from its roots in technological determinism and

infrastructure-driven approaches towards a more inclusive framework that fostered experimentation with novel problem-solving methods and the coordination of social interactions (Schuurman, 2015).

The digital city-initiatives were, more than the previous two predecessors, explicitly multi-stakeholder, as they explicitly included citizens (as users), policymakers (representing public organisations), and private organisations (businesses) within the initiative's framework. Thematically these initiatives also cover a broad range, albeit with a link to city life. Notably, user engagement is reconceptualized: citizens are no longer viewed solely as passive recipients of services but rather as potential co-creators with the technical infrastructure serving as a catalyst for this user-driven innovation (Ballon & Schuurman, 2015).

2.1.4 From “home labs” to “living labs”

The concept of living labs originated from MIT's Professor Mitchell, who referred to it as a specialised laboratory for observing and experimenting with daily home life, where research participants lived temporarily, treating it as a home-like environment. Initially, the focus was on testing new technologies in home-like settings, resembling what we now term the "American" notion of living labs. These living labs prioritised research on how ubiquitous computing technology could seamlessly integrate into the daily lives of inhabitants (Ballon & Schuurman, 2015). A distinguishing feature of these American living labs was their emphasis on human-centred design, in contrast to mere technological showcases. However, in most cases, users were primarily passive study subjects and not active participants in the development process.

The American notion of living labs marked the inception of a more refined concept associated with innovation, particularly with regard to infrastructure. Thematically, American living labs explored a wide range of innovations related to living and the home environment. This concept broadened the horizon for living labs as it shifted focus from technology-driven determinism to user-centric and innovation-oriented experimentation (Schuurman, 2015).

In summary, the contemporary living labs movement has its roots in three key antecedents from the latter part of the 20th century. The “cooperative design movement” fostered collaboration between users, designers, and researchers, emphasising a user-centric approach and real-life contexts. European social experiments promoted stakeholder involvement and mutual learning,

aligning with living labs' ethos of user engagement and experiential evaluation. Additionally, “digital city” initiatives signified a shift towards openness and innovation in urban living. Over time, the living labs concept evolved from technology testing in home-like settings to a user-centric, innovation-oriented approach, emphasising collaboration and real-world experimentation as its core principles. These antecedents have paved the way for the prominence of living labs in modern innovation and technology development.

2.2 Living Labs in Europe

According to ENoLL, the European Network of Living Labs, Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling up innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) joint value to the involved stakeholders. In this context, living labs operate as intermediaries/orchestrators of the Quadruple Helix (QH): citizens, research organisations, companies and government agencies/levels (ENoLL - European Network of Living Labs, 2023b).

From a methodological standpoint, contemporary living labs are dynamic networks composed of diverse actors, resources, and activities. These networks seamlessly integrate user-centred research and OI (Leminen, Westerlund, & Mika, 2012). From an infrastructural perspective, living labs can be considered as facilities designed to facilitate experimentation and co-creation in real-life environments (Bodi et al., 2021).

ENoLL has identified six key characteristics that are integral to European living labs (Bodi et al., 2021):

1. **Orchestration:** living labs act as orchestrators within the innovation ecosystem, forging connections, and partnerships with relevant stakeholders. The LL infrastructure itself serves as an active participant, collecting and processing user input and providing iterative feedback throughout the entire innovation process.
2. **Multi-Stakeholder Participation:** Embracing a holistic perspective of society, LLs engage stakeholders from the QH model, encompassing government, academia, the private sector, and citizens.

3. **Active User Involvement:** Successful innovation development is nowadays dependent on understanding both existing and emerging user needs, through which business opportunities are developed. For that purpose, the use of living labs has emerged as a novel form of creating competencies and competitive advantage. Indeed, LLs actively involve relevant stakeholders throughout all pertinent activities, ensuring that their feedback is not only captured but also implemented across the entire innovation lifecycle.

4. **Co-creation:** In a living lab, values are bottom-up co-created not only for but also by all relevant stakeholders, ensuring a higher adoption rate at the end.

5. **Real-Life Setting:** LLs operate within the real-life environment of end-users, seamlessly integrating innovations into their daily lives rather than relocating users to test sites for experimentation.

6. **Multi-Method Approach:** Each activity undertaken within a LL is driven by specific problems. Consequently, the methodological approach for each individual activity is selected based on the expected outcomes and the stakeholders involved.

In summary, LLs are characterised by active user involvement, real-life experimentation, a multi-method approach, and an innovation process grounded in co-creation. They are facilitated by a multi-stakeholder organisation, often described as a Public-Private-People partnership (Schuurman, 2015), which plays a pivotal role in orchestrating and nurturing these innovation ecosystems. These defining characteristics underscore the significance of LLs in the contemporary landscape of OI and user-centred research.

2.2.1 The Three-Layer Model

In light of the previous discussion, Schuurman (2015) proposes a clear distinction between three interconnected levels of analysis within the context of LLs. At the macro level, LLs are characterised as Public-Private-People partnerships organised to facilitate knowledge exchange and conduct innovation projects. The meso level encompasses the living lab innovation projects, characterised by active user involvement, co-creation, and multi-stakeholder engagement. Within these projects, various research steps are undertaken to elicit stakeholders' input and contributions, constituting the micro level.

2.2.1.1 Macro Level

At the macro level, the Open Innovation paradigm serves as the theoretical framework for comprehending living labs as networks involving diverse stakeholders collaborating on research and projects. Schuurman (2015) introduces the term "living lab constellation" to describe this macro-level context. As integral components of open innovation networks, living labs actively engage in both knowledge exploration, knowledge exploitation, and knowledge retention (See 1.3.1 Open Innovation and Living Labs).

In the realm of knowledge exploration LLs function as hubs for the exchange of ideas and collaborative research and development. Conversely characterised by the deliberate utilisation of existing (tacit and distributed) knowledge, LLs play a pivotal role in transforming this knowledge into tangible innovations.

As already underlined, according to Schurman (2015), living labs are innovation ecosystems that are managed and promoted by a multi-stakeholder organisation, defined as a Public-Private-People partnership. In these open innovation ecosystems, stakeholders are characterised by three key capacities: absorptive capacity (the ability to engage in knowledge exploration), desorptive capacity (the capability to engage in knowledge exploitation), and connective capacity (the capacity for knowledge retention) (Lichtenthaler, 2011).

The living lab Constellation

Stakeholders within living labs can be differentiated through the QH model, encompassing the public authorities/levels, the private sector, the academia and research institutes, and the civil society (Carayannis & Campbell, 2009), as well as their respective roles within the LL constellation: utilizers, enablers, providers, and users.

Utilizers in the LL ecosystem primarily engage in short-term cases to develop and test new products and services, strategically utilising living labs to collect data and collaborate with stakeholders, including end-users. Enablers, which may encompass public sector entities, non-governmental organisations, and financiers, provide essential resources and policy support to initiate and sustain LL operations. Providers, mainly private companies, contribute their product or service portfolios and manage material infrastructure for LL operations, focusing on co-development and aligning with business or industry needs. Users, or end-users, actively participate in LL operations and short-term cases, with some LLs involving existing user

groups or facilitating the formation of user communities (Leminen, Westerlund, & Mika, 2012).

While each participant holds a similar role and relevance within the network, variations may arise in terms of interests or activity levels, yet dominance by one party or the exercise of superior power is typically absent within the collaborative nature of open innovation networks. Living labs can be categorised based on the driving force behind their establishment (Leminen et al., 2012):

- Utilizer-driven LLs: Initiated by companies with the objective of enhancing their products and services, utilizer-driven LLs concentrate on the testing and refinement of their offerings, aligning closely with the firm's product development strategy. These LLs are notably characterised by a top-down coordination approach and an inhalation-dominated participation approach, meaning that the activities within the LL are initiated and oriented towards fulfilling the needs of the driving party by engaging other stakeholders in innovation activities (Leminen, 2013).
- Enabler-driven LLs: Facilitating collaboration among key actors stands as a significant outcome, given the imperative of multi-party cooperation for sustained regional development. Enabler-driven LLs adopt a bottom-up coordination approach and an exhalation-dominated participation approach, signifying a strategy that primarily addresses the requirements and preferences of stakeholders rather than serving the needs of a single driving actor.
- Provider-driven LLs: These LLs emerge as a result of initiatives undertaken by various development organisations, including educational institutes, universities, or consultants. Provider-driven LLs typically employ a top-down coordination approach while employing an exhalation-dominated participation approach.
- User-driven living labs: Established by user communities, User-driven LLs are dedicated to addressing the everyday problems faced by users in alignment with their values and needs. The primary focus revolves around identifying solutions that align with user expectations and requirements. These LLs are characterised by a bottom-up approach and an inhalation-dominated participation approach.

This stakeholder model underscores the close alignment of the LL concept with the OI paradigm, highlighting the symbiotic nature of stakeholder roles. In Leminen et al.'s (2012) typology, academic researchers are categorised as providers due to their expertise in user research, emphasising their vital contribution to the living lab ecosystem. Beyond user research, academia's role extends to technical research related to the living lab's focus and research on policy and business matters, warranting their recognition as a distinct actor within the living lab constellation (Schuurman, 2015).

Figure 2 - The Anatomy of a Living Lab Constellation
(Schuurman, 2015)

In conclusion, the comprehensive framework delineated here offers an understanding of LLs as multifaceted innovation ecosystems. At the macro level, the adoption of the OI paradigm as the overarching theoretical framework illuminates LLs as dynamic networks that engage in both knowledge exploration, exploitation and retention. The coexistence of absorptive, desorptive, and connective capacities among stakeholders underscores their pivotal role in shaping the LL constellation. Furthermore, the application of the QH model serves as a valuable lens through which to differentiate the roles of government, the private sector, academia, and civil society within these ecosystems. The taxonomy of LLs, categorised based on their driving forces, underscores their adaptability and responsiveness to diverse innovation needs and aspirations. Ultimately, this framework not only elucidates the intricate structure and function of LLs but also accentuates their profound alignment with the OI paradigm, positioning them as crucial hubs for collaborative and user-centric innovation in contemporary landscape.

2.2.1.2 Meso Level

At the meso level of analysis, we can identify the living lab projects within the broader context of LL constellations. These LL projects are characterised by collaboration among various actors, including end-users, and are influenced by theoretical frameworks such as Open Innovation and User Innovation paradigms. At this level of analysis, both of these frameworks are applicable since LL projects entail cooperation among diverse stakeholders, including end users, for the purpose of innovation (Schuurman, 2015).

In the proposed conceptual model of a LL, infrastructure plays a central role as it serves as a facilitator for collaboration among all actors involved. This infrastructure not only enables collaboration but also facilitates the exchange of knowledge and technology within the innovation ecosystem (Schuurman et al., 2016). As highlighted in the previous chapter, such knowledge and technology spillovers are integral components of the OI strategy adopted by businesses and organisations (Chesbrough & Bogers, 2013).

Living Labs' Building Blocks

Veekman et al. (2013) have identified 11 building blocks and 3 pillars that constitute the foundation of LL projects: Building Blocks of the Living Lab Environment, Building Blocks of the Living Lab Approach and Innovation Outcome. While Pillar 1 covers both the macro and meso levels, Pillar 2, the LL approach refers to the meso level only.

Figure 3 - The Living Lab Triangle: The triangulation between environment, approach, and outcome in living labs

(Veekman et al., 2013)

Pillar 1: Building Blocks of the Living Lab Environment

1. **Technical Infrastructure:** living labs should provide the necessary technical components for testing and co-creating innovations. Ideally, this includes monitoring the technical performance of innovations during both usage and non-usage phases.
2. **Ecosystem Approach:** A diverse set of stakeholders, including industrial partners, users, and research organisations, collaborates within the LL ecosystem to develop and evaluate processes, products, or services. Creating and sharing value is crucial to attracting and retaining members within this ecosystem, fostering long-term engagement.
3. **Level of Openness:** LLs adhere to the principle of openness in the innovation process to encourage a multitude of perspectives and accelerate development. This openness extends to intellectual property rights and the willingness to embrace new partners.
4. **Community:** Users participating in LLs become part of a community, which can take various forms, spanning from a “community of interest” (CoI) to a “community of practice” (CoP). Community of interest includes all the stakeholders you’re involving in your project. The primary goal of CoP in a LL is to engage a diverse range of individuals and stakeholders who are interested in the outcomes or developments related to a particular project or innovation. Within the community of interest, there is one or more communities of practice, representing the people involved in each step of the project and usually have a strong focus on a particular area of expertise, they emerge by themselves. Members of a CoP engage regularly and work together day by day to advance the project. The primary goals of CoP in a LL are to foster innovation, best practices and the development of new solutions within a specific domain. Understanding the motivations of users is essential to maintain their engagement.
5. **Lifespan:** The duration of a LL is a defining characteristic. It refers to the duration of the LL, and not of a single innovation project launched within the lab. For example, a short-term LL initiative might last less than six months, whereas a long-term initiative might have a two-year duration, and a very long-term initiative might have an indeterminate end date.
6. **Scale:** The number of users involved in LL research activities, such as the LL panel, determines the scale of the initiative.
7. **Real-World Context:** LLs operate in a real-world context, bridging the gap between innovation and practical application.

Pillar 2: Building Blocks of the Living Lab Approach

1. Evaluation, Context Research, and Co-Creation: Test users actively participate throughout the innovation cycle, offering feedback, evaluation, and co-creation opportunities. Co-creation should be iterative and employ participatory methods, considering the critical influence of usage context.
2. User Role: Based on the degree of user activity and the firm's approach to co-creation, Leminen et al. (2012) have identified four distinct user roles:
 - Informant: These users share valuable insights and information, offering feedback and suggestions based on their experiences and preferences. They play a passive role, primarily providing knowledge and input.
 - Tester: They actively evaluate innovations, providing feedback on usability, functionality, and performance. They help identify issues and contribute to refining the innovation.
 - Contributor: These users engage in the development and co-creation process, offering ideas and contributing to design and development. They play an active role in shaping innovation.
 - Co-creators: Highly engaged users collaborate closely with the project team in designing, developing, and co-producing innovations. They have a significant impact on the final product, serving as true partners in the co-creation process.

Pillar 3: The Innovation Outcome

To evaluate the success of a LL, it is crucial to consider the innovation outcome. This pillar establishes a direct link between the building blocks of a LL setup and the outcomes of innovation projects within the lab. This analysis acknowledges the intentional and unintentional influence of the LL environment on projects. By examining these characteristics across different LLs, we can draw conclusions about how to structure these building blocks and their impact on innovation project outcomes. On section 2.2.2 Impact Assessment and Evaluation of Living Labs this link will be deepened and analysed.

The Living Lab Integrative Process

Mastelic (2019) introduced the concept of the Living Labs Integrative Process (LLIP) to outline the various stages undertaken in a LL project.

Figure 4 - The Living Lab Iterative Process. Adapted from Mastelic 2019.

(ENoLL - European Network of Living Labs, 2023a)

The LLIP is designed as an iterative process that requires continuous monitoring throughout its various stages. Rooted in the principles of Design Thinking (Spagnoli, 2023) and Community-based Social Marketing, this process facilitates the development of human-centric innovations (Mastelic, 2019; Spagnoli, 2023; Vervoort, 2022). It consists of seven distinct steps, guiding the progression from the problem space to the deployment space, through the solution space.

Problem Space: The initial phase focuses on gaining a comprehensive understanding of the challenge, problem, need, or requirement at hand. It involves identifying key stakeholders, determining the necessary technical perspectives, and formulating precise questions to define the customer need or problem clearly.

Step 1 - Empathise - select a practice: The initial step involves a thorough analysis of available data within the ecosystem. This includes understanding the context, identifying one to three critical practices or issues with significant ecosystem impacts, and structuring the living lab. This includes defining long-term goals, establishing a shared vision, and addressing the root

causes of identified problems. This organisational step also includes the scoping of the needed roles and responsibilities within the governance of the living lab.

Step 2 - Empathise - integrate stakeholders: The focus shifts to identifying all relevant stakeholders who need active involvement. As the living lab project takes shape, stakeholder mapping using the QH model ensures the inclusion of essential participants. (Mastelic, 2019; Spagnoli, 2023; Vervoort, 2022)

Step 3 - Define: In this phase, the process seeks to uncover barriers and validate assumptions by individually engaging with key stakeholders. It also involves preparatory steps to ensure a trusted and safe environment for all involved stakeholders (Mastelic, 2019; Vervoort, 2022).

Solution Space: This space focuses on generating innovative solutions and determining how to implement them effectively (Spagnoli, 2023; Vervoort, 2022).

Step 4 - Ideate: During this step, creative ideas are generated, and concepts are explored while diverging from traditional approaches. Techniques such as brainstorming, mind-mapping, and sketching are employed to generate a wide range of ideas. The goal is to discover the best solution through testing and feedback (Spagnoli, 2023; Vervoort, 2022).

Step 5 - Prototype: Prototyping is utilised as an interactive tool to explore different options and consider user expectations. Prototypes can take various forms, from minimum viable products to services or experiences. Real-life experimentation in the field helps identify any missing elements or issues before a complete rollout (Spagnoli, 2023; Vervoort, 2022).

Step 6 - Test: During the testing stage of the LLIP, a rigorous evaluation of performance and impact takes place. This critical phase revolves around the interaction and feedback received from users, fostering iterative cycles essential for refining solutions. Importantly, it serves as a formalisation of knowledge, offering invaluable opportunities to learn from both successes and failures. Furthermore, it encompasses a broader spectrum that includes non-users and facilitates the transfer of knowledge within and beyond the living lab project. Within this phase, multiple evaluation models and frameworks come into play. These established frameworks provide a structured approach to evaluate and assess the effectiveness of the solutions under scrutiny (Vervoort, 2022).

This evaluation phase is characterised by iterative loops and feedback mechanisms that empower continuous improvement over time. It plays a pivotal role in the refinement of products and services, aligning them more closely with evolving needs and objectives.

When addressing impact assessments, having a deep understanding of the tangible outcomes of activities and previous phases of the LL project becomes paramount. This knowledge empowers project stakeholders to discern which approaches yield the best results and to quantify the direct, indirect, and diffuse impacts. Such insights not only inform the optimization of ongoing innovation efforts but also guide decisions related to broadening or deepening the scope of the project and, importantly, scaling up its impact (Mastelic, 2019).

Deployment Space: This phase extends beyond the living lab project and focuses on market readiness (Spagnoli, 2023; Vervoort, 2022).

Step 7 - Implement: During implementation, the co-created solution is put into an operational environment, necessitating actions related to legal, privacy, socio-economic, and environmental considerations to make it work effectively (Spagnoli, 2023).

Step 8 - Scale Up: The final step involves testing solutions outside the initial project scope. The LL evaluates the balance between expectations and reality, analyses and updates the main goal of the LL, and defines or refines new long-term strategies based on past and current performance conditions (Spagnoli, 2023).

The Living Labs Integrative Process, with its three distinct spaces and eight sequential steps, serves as a comprehensive framework for the development of innovative solutions, emphasising human-centric design and continuous improvement throughout the project lifecycle.

In conclusion, our exploration of LL projects within the broader context of LL constellations reveals a dynamic and collaborative innovation ecosystem that integrates theoretical frameworks like Open Innovation and User Innovation. At its core, the success of LLs hinges on a well-designed infrastructure that fosters collaboration and facilitates the exchange of crucial knowledge and technology spillovers. The framework proposed by Veeckman et al. (2013), comprising 11 building blocks and 3 pillars, provides a comprehensive perspective on the essential elements of LLs, spanning technical infrastructure, open innovation principles, user engagement, and innovation outcomes. As we delve deeper into the dynamics of LLs, it

becomes evident that the interplay between the LL environment and its projects plays a vital role in shaping innovation outcomes.

Furthermore, the Living Labs Integrative Process presented by Mastelic (2019) offers a structured and iterative approach to driving innovation in LL projects. This process emphasises human-centric design, continuous improvement, and scalability throughout the project lifecycle. It serves as a valuable guide for organisations and researchers seeking to harness the full potential of LLs to drive innovation and create meaningful impact.

Together, these insights highlight the significance of LLs as catalysts for innovation and knowledge exchange, shedding light on the intricate interplay between infrastructure, collaboration, and project outcomes within this dynamic ecosystem.

2.2.1.3 Micro Level

The research activities within a living lab project, termed "micro-level" in this context, draw upon the theoretical foundations of the User Innovation model and the User-Centred Design (UCD)/Participatory Design (PD) paradigms. LLs are conceptualised as an approach to engage users in innovation processes through value co-creation (Schuurman, 2015).

At the micro level, the LL research activities encompass the steps undertaken in LL projects, specifically focusing on individual user involvement activities. These activities leverage the resources and capabilities of the LL organisation and involve the engagement of users and stakeholders through a combination of various methods and tools (European Commission et al., 2021). Several valuable resources aiding in the selection of suitable methods and tools include:

- Unalab Co-creation Toolkit: <https://unalab.enoll.org/>
- Social & Creative MED Community Toolkit: <https://taliamed.enoll.org/>
- The SISCODE Toolbox for Co-creation Journeys:
<https://siscodeproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/toolkit-27092019-1.pdf>
- Coco Toolkit of Laurea: <https://www.laurea.fi/en/cocotoolkit/>
- IMEC's User Innovation Toolkit: <https://userinnovationtoolkit.ugent.be/#/methods>

- SCORE Co-create your City Toolkit: <https://www.ihs.nl/en/advisory-training-andresearch/tools-and-toolkits/co-create-your-city-toolkit>

Classifying Living Labs: Innovation Processes and Tool Utilization Framework

Leminen and Westerlund (2017) have proposed a framework for classifying LLs based on their characteristics regarding the innovation process and tool usage. This framework comprises two dimensions: the innovation process, ranging from "predefined, linear" to "iterative, nonlinear," and the utilisation of tools, spanning from "standardised" to "customised." This two-dimensional framework aids in understanding how methods and tools support the comprehension of innovation activities within LLs, categorising them based on their alignment with the innovation process (linear or iterative).

The study scrutinises and categorises the type of tools employed to foster innovation within LLs. These tools encompass open communication and ideation tools, which promote, collect, evaluate, and disseminate contributions, as well as monitoring tools used for tracking activities and individual contributions for potential legal purposes. The analyses reveal four primary ways in which tools contribute to innovation activities in LLs: linearizers, iterators, tailors, and mass customizers (Figure 5).

Figure 5 - A conceptual framework for categorising living labs based on their innovation process and tools.

(Leminen & Westerlund, 2017)

1. Linearizers concentrate on employing a linear innovation process alongside a standardised set of predefined tools. Linearizers favour a structured but linear innovation process, where the use of standardised tools typically results in incremental

innovation. These LLs often represent utilizer- and provider-driven entities, managed by organisations striving for operational efficiency. The tools developed cover various phases of innovation, catering to diverse customer-centric and customer-driven methods. Consequently, LL activities are frequently productized and commercialised, with the generalised tools being adaptable to varying customer requirements.

2. Iterators, akin to linearizers, seek solutions using a standardised set of tools within their innovation processes. However, unlike linearizers, iterators adjust their innovation processes based on experiences and learning from ongoing activities. Surprisingly, only a few examples of iterators were found among the 40 LLs sampled by Leminen and Westerlund (2017), speculating that many have not yet aligned their innovation practices with predefined toolsets.
3. Mass customizers. The majority of LLs appear to align with the mass customizers archetype. Many provider-driven, utilizer-driven, and enabler-driven LLs fall into this category. Mass customizers employ customised tools within a linear, standardised innovation process, typically leading to incremental innovation. While the assortment of tools offers the potential for radical innovation, the standardised innovation process often confines the required innovation activities. Mass customizers streamline innovation processes through predefined linear approaches to enhance efficiency. Nevertheless, the flexibility in innovation activities stems from the customised tools employed in LLs.
4. Tailors, akin to mass customizers, customise tool usage and, similarly to iterators, adopt iterative, non-linear innovation processes. Employing tools innovatively within an iterative, nonlinear process fosters the emergence of radical innovations. Tailors seek tailored solutions for innovation needs by adjusting both the innovation process and tool utilisation.

This framework by Leminen and Westerlund (2017) illuminates innovation activities and their association with diverse LLs. While emerging LLs may initially adopt a customised approach to explore the potential of LL activities, the results of this study indicate that LLs tend to streamline their operations through standardised tools, standardised innovation processes, or both. Standardisation is often aimed at reducing costs and realising cost savings. However, the study suggests that such standardisation tends to yield incremental innovations within LLs, potentially diminishing enthusiasm among stakeholders. This finding aligns with prior research emphasising the importance of passion, in addition to resources and knowledge, in LL activities

(Leminen, Westerlund, & Mika, 2012; Leminen & Westerlund, 2012). Finally, the study puts forth three propositions:

1. Standardised tools reduce the complexity of innovation activities, leading to predefined incremental innovation outcomes in LLs.
2. A predefined linear innovation process reduces the complexity of innovation activities, resulting in predefined incremental innovation outcomes.
3. Embracing an iterative, non-linear innovation process and customised tools for innovation activities heightens the likelihood of undefined and novel innovation outcomes.

In summary, the micro-level research activities within LLs are rooted in the User Innovation model and principles of User-Centred Design/Participatory Design. The framework by Leminen and Westerlund (2017) categorises LLs based on their innovation processes and tool utilisation, revealing four distinct tool usage patterns: linearizers, iterators, mass customizers, and tailors. These patterns shed light on how tools influence innovation within LLs. The study underscores the prevalent adoption of standardised tools and processes in LLs, often driven by cost reduction motives, resulting in incremental innovations. Nonetheless, it emphasises the indispensable role of passion alongside resources and knowledge for thriving LL activities.

This exploration illuminates the dynamics of LL research activities, providing insights into their foundation, operational methodologies, and potential avenues for enhancing innovation outcomes.

2.2.2 Impact Assessment and Evaluation of Living Labs

Assessing the impact of LLs presents significant challenges due to the intricate nature of measuring outcomes within dynamic and evolving innovation environments. Methodologies for impact assessment must be adaptable and flexible to effectively capture the diverse range of impacts generated by LLs. Despite various attempts to establish a common framework for measuring the impact of LLs on innovation outcomes by scholars such as Stahlbrost (2012), Leminen et al. (2012), Veeckman et al. (2013), Schuurman et al. (2016), and Mastelic (2019), Paskaleva and Cooper (2021) assert a scarcity of evidence in the public domain regarding the effectiveness of employing the LL methodology.

In their investigation encompassing 49 sources discussing LLs' key characteristics, Paskaleva & Cooper selected 24 sources likely to provide comprehensive descriptions of these characteristics, with 13 sources outlining claimed benefits derived from LLs. However, their findings reveal a limited consensus on what constitutes the core components of LLs, with general agreement confined to aspects such as innovation, user engagement, services, co-creation, and product development. This lack of consensus extends to the benefits associated with LLs, where claims of advantages often rest on the descriptive rather than empirical evidence, creating a tautological relationship where LLs deliver benefits because of their inherent characteristics. However, the evidence LLs authors provide regarding the benefits is often lacking in detail, making it challenging to assess its quality and reliability. Therefore, Paskaleva & Cooper argue that the available evidence falls short in providing a clear demonstration of the effectiveness of the LL methodology, with existing evidence rated low in both strength and quality across various evaluation scales.

2.2.2.1 New approaches

In response to the assertions made by Paskaleva and Cooper (2021), Vervoort et al. (2022) have undertaken the development of a new harmonised evaluation framework for LLs, aiming to facilitate the assessment of LLs at macro-, meso-, and micro-levels. The evaluation framework for LLs has been developed on analysis and collaboration among various LL networks, including the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) and Le Forum des Living Labs en Santé et Autonomie (Forum LLSA), as well as involvement in different European projects such as oPEN lab¹, SCORE², Rewaise³, and WATER-MINING⁴, wherein LLs are conceived, developed, and evaluated.

As we know, ENoLL has identified six LLs' key characteristics, over time they served as a reference to construct around them an evaluation framework with six key chapters and fifteen weighted criteria:

¹ <https://openlab-project.eu/>

² [Smart control of the climate resilience in European coastal cities - Score \(score-eu-project.eu\)](#)

³ [rewaise – Resilient Water InnovationEconomy](#)

⁴ <https://watermining.eu>

- **Organisation:** this first chapter deals with the organisation, management, and governance of Living Labs.
- **Users & Reality:** this chapter evaluates how the Living Lab is dealing with all different kinds of user engagement & how its processes are deployed in real-life settings.
- **Resources:** this chapter describes the different available resources of the Living Lab (infrastructures, materials...) and their potential use/service.
- **Openness:** this chapter looks at the general approach towards open innovation and the inclusion of all the groups of the QH.
- **Value:** this chapter looks at the outcomes of the Living Lab and how they create values and benefits for all the involved stakeholders of the Living Lab.
- **Business Model & plans for the future:** this chapter evaluates your current business model (BM) and accessibility to funding and looks at your SWOT analysis and strategic plan for the future to investigate the sustainability of the Living Lab.

<i>Current</i>	<i>New</i>
Organisation	Strategy (macro)
<i>Organisation, management & governance (macro)</i>	<i>Governance</i>
<i>Experience in living lab operations (all)</i>	<i>Business model</i>
<i>Interest & ability to participate in innovation system mechanisms (all)</i>	<i>Culture</i>
Users & reality	Operations (all levels)
<i>Iterative living lab process & real-life settings (meso-micro)</i>	<i>Operations</i>
<i>Users & people engagement approach (all)</i>	<i>Human Resources</i>
<i>Quality of methods and tools(meso-micro)</i>	<i>Equipment & infrastructure</i>
Resources	Openness (all levels)
<i>Roles & responsibilities of qualified staff (macro)</i>	<i>Innovation processes & partnerships</i>
<i>Access & availability of equipment & infrastructures (all)</i>	<i>Ownership of results</i>
<i>Internal & external communication (macro – meso)</i>	Users & reality (all levels)
Openness	<i>Quality of the iterative LL processes in real-life settings</i>
<i>Openness of innovation processes and partnerships (macro)</i>	<i>User-centricity of the user & stakeholder engagement approach</i>
<i>Feedback protection & author's rights (macro-meso)</i>	<i>Quality of participatory tools & methods</i>
Value	Impact & value creation (all levels)
<i>Co-created values for all involved stakeholders (all)</i>	<i>Co-created values</i>
<i>Coverage of the value chain (all)</i>	<i>Impacts of the living lab</i>
Business model & future plans	Stability & harmonisation (macro)
<i>Business model & access/ability to funding (macro)</i>	<i>Stability of the living lab (macro)</i>
<i>SWOT analysis & strategic plans for the future (macro)</i>	<i>Harmonization & scale up</i>

Table 2 - Comparison of current and new evaluation chapters and criteria.

(Vervoort et al., 2022)

The process of refining the evaluation framework involved a comprehensive literature review for contextual understanding, comparative analysis to identify gaps, iterative online workshops, and scrutiny of applications for ENoLL membership to delineate a new framework. This effort resulted in the retention of the six chapters, addressing different facets of LLs' operations, and fifteen criteria, with adjustments made to ensure harmonisation and transparency, including the classification of each (sub)criteria according to macro-, meso-, and micro-levels. Table 2 (Vervoort et al., 2022) shows the differences between the two sets of evaluation criteria.

1. Strategy - This chapter focuses on the macro-level of a LL, considering the multi-stakeholder participation and the orchestration role of the LL, looking at their collaboration strategies, while investigating the BM of the LL as well. Within this chapter the LL is evaluated against three criteria:

- Governance
- Business Model
- Culture

2. Operations - This chapter covers all levels of a LL, looking at the way the LL manages its operations. Within this chapter of the evaluation, three criteria are defined:

- Operations
- Human Resources
- Equipment and Infrastructure

3. Openness - This chapter investigates the openness of the LL from a macro-, meso- and microlevel perspective, by focusing on the processes, the partnerships, the feedback & IP protection. Within this chapter of the evaluation two criteria are defined:

- Innovation processes & partnerships
- Ownership of results

4. Users & Reality - This chapter investigates the ways of collaboration with users and the levels of engagement & participation.

Therefore, it relates to the macro-, meso- and micro-level of a LL. Within this chapter of the evaluation, three criteria are defined:

- Quality of the iterative LL processes in real-life settings
- User-centricity of the user & stakeholder engagement approach
- Quality of participatory tools and methods

5. Impact & Value Creation - This chapter assesses the co-created values (e.g., knowledge sharing, capacity building, network building) by whom but even more importantly for whom. Furthermore, it investigates different impact aspects of the LL. Therefore, this chapter is related to all levels of a LL. Within this chapter of the evaluation two criteria are defined:

- Co-created values
- Impact of the Living Lab, in terms of:
 - internal impact corresponding to what degree did the different levels of the LL learned from each other (macro-meso-micro);
 - societal impact (e.g., behavioural change, inclusion, diversity, digital gap) (macro-meso);
 - economic impact (e.g., patents, market disruption, speed of market penetration, decrease of cost, increase of profit, improved value proposition of the LL) (macro-meso);
 - environmental impact (e.g., reduction of pollution, decrease of weather events, increase of air quality) (macro-meso);
 - regulatory impact (e.g., public policies, standardisation of regulatory requirements, marketing authorization) (macro-meso).

6. Stability & Harmonization - The final chapter focuses on the (financial) stability of the LL from a macro-level perspective, considering different needed aspects like BM, service offerings and strategy plans. Aligned with this, this chapter looks at the level of harmonisation of these strategic and operational building blocks beyond the LL (in relationship to other LLs, RIs and open innovation orchestrators) since this will increase the sustainability of the LL.

Consequently, it mainly deals with the macro level. Within this chapter of the evaluation two criteria are defined:

- Stability of the LL
- Harmonisation & scaling-up

This comprehensive evaluation structure (Vervoort et al., 2022) offers a harmonised approach to assess LLs across multiple levels, with particular emphasis on the macro level, fostering a long-term vision towards sustainability. It not only aids evaluators and LL networks in understanding the potential operational levels of LLs but also facilitates individual LLs in conducting regular self-assessments based on the six key building blocks and fifteen criteria. Such an approach aligns with the call for a more evidence-based understanding of LLs' performance, as advocated by Paskaleva and Cooper (2021), thereby contributing to the advancement of a sustainable LL architecture.

2.2.3 Living Labs in the EU Research and Innovation Strategy

Horizon Europe, the European Union's flagship research and innovation funding program spanning from 2021 to 2027, stands as the foremost multinational initiative of its kind globally, endowed with a substantial budget of approximately €95.5 billion (European Commission - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2021). This program is designed to catalyse scientific excellence, drive innovation, and confront societal challenges by nurturing research and innovation endeavours across diverse domains. Positioned within the broader ambit of the United Nations' (2015) 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, Horizon Europe dovetails with the international community's commitment to realise 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030. These goals encompass eradicating poverty, fostering sustainable and inclusive development, safeguarding human rights, and ensuring inclusivity in progress.

Crucially, Horizon Europe integrates the SDGs as guiding principles throughout its research and innovation initiatives across various thematic domains. Projects funded under this program are expressly tasked with addressing one or more SDGs, thereby aligning research endeavours with the overarching global agenda for sustainable development. By foregrounding cross-cutting themes such as climate action, circular economy, digitalization, and social innovation, Horizon Europe endeavours to address multifaceted challenges comprehensively, fostering collaboration among diverse stakeholders to amplify the impact of research and innovation

efforts on sustainable development objectives. The program's structure is organised into three main pillars, each delineating distinct objectives and priorities.

Pillar 1, "Excellent Science," is dedicated to nurturing frontier research, fortifying the European Research Area, and consolidating Europe's leadership in scientific pursuits.

Pillar 2, "Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness," encompasses endeavours to tackle societal challenges ranging from health and climate change to clean energy and digitalization, while concurrently bolstering industrial competitiveness and fostering innovation across sectors.

Pillar 3, "Innovative Europe," is geared toward enhancing the EU's innovation capacity, fostering the development and adoption of transformative technologies, and facilitating the growth of innovative enterprises, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

A defining feature of Horizon Europe is its reliance on Missions. The Missions under Horizon Europe serve as direct enablers of key priorities such as the European Green Deal, Europe's Beating Cancer Plan, An economy that works for people, the New European Bauhaus, and the EU's renewed industrial competitiveness agenda, while also contributing to the European Space Programme (European Commission - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2021). This alignment is aimed at addressing critical challenges while adhering to the overarching framework of the SDGs (European Commission, 2021e).

Central to the success of Missions is the clear articulation of objectives and a shared agreement on their realisation timeline. The impact is derived from the Missions' ability to mobilise diverse stakeholders, ranging from various levels of government to researchers, innovators, educational institutions, businesses of varying scales, investors, and civil society, all united behind concrete and achievable objectives (European Commission - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation & Mazzucato, 2018). Rooted in research and innovation, missions embark from clear starting points, each delineating concrete targets that guide the direction of research and innovation endeavours. Unlike traditional research projects, mission objectives encompass a broader spectrum, fostering a portfolio of research and innovation actions spanning basic and applied research across various sectors and domains. Emphasising demonstration, scalability, and replication of both existing and novel solutions, including social innovations, missions adopt a tailored innovation approach adaptable to local contexts (European Commission, 2021e). EU Missions epitomise an innovative collaborative model

aimed at addressing challenges and enhancing the quality of life for European citizens and beyond. The concrete targets set forth by missions, with a defined timeline for attainment by 2030, offer a tangible metric for measuring success and rallying support across European countries, sectors, and disciplines.

The European Union has outlined five distinct Missions for Horizon Europe (European Commission, 2021e):

- Adaptation to Climate Change: support at least 150 European regions and communities to become climate resilient by 2030.
- Cancer: improving the lives of more than 3 million people by 2030 through prevention, cure and for those affected by cancer including their families, to live longer and better.
- Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030
- 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030
- A Soil Deal for Europe: 100 living labs and lighthouses to lead the transition towards healthy soils by 2030.

The European Green Deal (European Commission, 2019) underscored the imperative for the Research and Innovation (R&I) agenda to adopt a systemic approach in order to attain its ambitious objectives. Given the complexity and interconnected nature of contemporary challenges, effective solutions demand a multifaceted perspective from various disciplines and sectors. The Horizon Europe Strategic Plan 2025–2027 Analysis (European Commission - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, 2023) marks that:

"Under these circumstances, innovation experts and scholars have put forward a strong claim for policymakers to provide an R&I policy mix that sets the direction of change and the framework conditions to navigate the transition process, notably spaces for experimentation (including living labs), with novel policy instruments and synergies between them, inclusive and coherent governance settings, and consultation and engagement with stakeholders (such as the multi-actor approach) throughout the R&I cycles."

Accordingly, R&I policies should serve as catalysts for transformation, facilitating the shift towards sustainable development. This involves empowering individuals and communities to

address societal needs while fostering the creation of sustainable, inclusive, and resilient societies. Additionally, due consideration must be given to aspects beyond mere functionality, encompassing elements like quality of experience and the sense of belonging:

"[F]or instance, ex ante policy experimentation and real-time monitoring and evaluation could be more widely integrated into policymaking processes [...]. Living labs are an example of ex ante experimental interventions that promote delivering on manifold, locally adapted solutions. Moreover, experimentation could support formulating and implementing adaptive policy mixes, to which policy instruments could be gradually introduced to support the different stages of the change."

A comprehensive, whole-of-government, and whole-of-society approach is critical to guide public and private sector actors, ensuring coordination and integration across stakeholders, government levels, and policy domains. Furthermore,

"Deep transformations require R&I policy support not only for disruptive and other types of innovations but also, and most importantly, for upscaling, replication, and acceleration of these innovations. That is why R&I policy also needs to fully embrace the principles underpinning transformative change towards sustainable development – transformation, directionality, co-creation, diffusion and uptake."

This is a compelling call to action for LLs to bring about these transformative changes.

2.2.3.2 The Role of Living Labs - How are Living Labs integrated and are they supporting the goals of Horizon Europe?

Living labs are emerging as vital instruments for achieving the ambitious goals outlined in Horizon Europe. Acting as dynamic spaces for long-term, site-specific, and multi-stakeholder experimentation of innovative sustainable solutions, they stand as essential tools in furthering the objectives outlined in the four Green Deal Missions: Adaptation to Climate Change, Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030, 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities by 2030 and A Soil Deal for Europe (European Commission, 2021d). Interestingly, they also play a role in addressing challenges related to Cancer research (European Commission, 2021c).

Bridging the Knowledge-Action Gap

LLs bridge the gap between scientific knowledge, policy formulation, and societal action, facilitating the translation of research into practical solutions. (European Commission - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2023; European Commission, 2021b).

Orchestrating Open Innovation Networks

LLs facilitate stakeholder and citizen engagement through open science and participatory innovation, ensuring that the development and implementation of solutions are inclusive and responsive to the needs of communities. By orchestrating collaboration among diverse stakeholders, LLs foster awareness and inclusivity among decision-makers, private sectors, NGOs, and the public at large (European Commission - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2023; European Commission, 2021c).

Incubating and Scaling Innovation

LLs serve as incubators for innovation, they play a crucial role in fostering collaboration among traditional and non-traditional innovators facilitating the demonstration and dissemination of technologies and practices. (European Commission, 2021a, 2021b).

Tailoring Solutions

LLs pioneer, showcase, and accelerate the adoption of innovative solutions tailored to diverse geographical and socio-economic contexts. They provide environments for trialling, evaluating, and refining innovations in situ, gathering valuable feedback for iterative improvement (European Commission, 2021b, 2021c).

Enhancing Dialogue and Trust

LLs serve as points of contact with European citizens at various levels, fostering dialogue, trust, and direct feedback on EU activities and policies. Moreover, LLs increase the accessibility to knowledge avoiding a two-speed society (European Commission - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation et al., 2023; European Commission, 2021c).

Notable LLs are considered valuable means for their capacities related both to knowledge exploration, exploitation and retention. Confirming Lichtenthaler's (2011) hypothesis that, in

the light of the three OI processes, outside-in, inside-out, and coupled, OI networks demand three corresponding organisation capabilities:

- absorptive capacity, or the ability to deal with knowledge exploration;
- desorptive capacity or the ability to deal with knowledge exploitation;
- connective capacity or the ability to deal with knowledge retention.

The desorptive capacity is what makes LLs a crucial asset in the EU R&I Toolbox.

2.2.3.3 Solving the European Paradox?

A persistent challenge for the European Union is the "European Paradox," or the gap between research leadership and the commercial success of innovation (European Commission, 1996). Almirall and Wareham (2011) reframed this paradox through the lens of OI principles, positing that while Europe excels in research (exploration), it lags in achieving market success (exploitation).

Almirall and Wareham (2008, 2011) propose LLs as a potential solution to bridge this gap. They facilitate the surfacing of tacit, experiential, and domain-specific knowledge within real-world settings. This aligns with Schuurman's (2015) view of LLs as tools for distributed innovation driven by co-creation among diverse actors, including users.

Furthermore, Almirall and Wareham (2008) suggest that LLs can empower user communities with entrepreneurial inclinations. This aligns with the convergence of User Innovation and OI perspectives, where users are not just passive participants but active contributors to the innovation process. This user empowerment can be particularly valuable in bridging the pre-commercial gap by generating initial user demand for in-development innovations, thereby promoting user involvement in the exploitation phase. Second, they can orchestrate the actions of stakeholders, facilitating knowledge exchange and aligning inputs into the innovation process, thus contributing to knowledge exploration.

Schuurman's study (2015) corroborates the hypothesis proposed by Almirall and Wareham (2008, 2011) regarding the dynamics of LLs. Schurman investigated the efficacy of four LL constellations, engaging 58 stakeholders in total. Among these stakeholders, 30 prioritised knowledge exploration, while 28 focused on knowledge exploitation. The findings revealed

that stakeholders pursuing exploration goals demonstrated a higher success rate (73%) compared to those prioritising exploitation (61%). Nevertheless, these results underscore the capability of LLs to facilitate knowledge exploitation in practical contexts, highlighting a nuanced interplay between exploration and exploitation dynamics.

To sum up, Horizon Europe stands as a pivotal initiative in fostering research and innovation on a global scale, strategically aligned with the UN's 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. The program's emphasis on cross-cutting themes and its multifaceted approach through Missions position it to effectively address complex societal challenges. Notably, LLs emerge as a crucial instrument for achieving Horizon Europe's ambitious goals.

LLs act as dynamic spaces that bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical implementation. They facilitate experimentation, stakeholder engagement, and the dissemination of innovative solutions tailored to local contexts. This fosters knowledge exchange and empowers diverse actors, including user communities, to co-create and refine solutions that address the multifaceted challenges outlined in Horizon Europe's Missions.

Furthermore, LLs hold the potential to bridge the "European Paradox". Their capacity for knowledge exploration and exploitation aligns with the principles of OI, fostering a dynamic knowledge exchange that spurs innovation and facilitates the transition of research findings into marketable solutions.

2.3 Conclusions

In conclusion, this chapter has traced the evolution of LLs, from their 20th-century antecedents in Cooperative Design and social experimentation to their contemporary prominence as instruments of OI. Living Labs have fundamentally reshaped the innovation process by prioritising active user engagement, real-world experimentation, and co-creation, all facilitated by robust multi-stakeholder partnerships.

We have delved into the multifaceted world of LLs, focusing on three interconnected levels of analysis: macro, meso, and micro. Each level offers unique insights into the structure, dynamics, and outcomes of LLs.

At the macro level, we have characterised LLs as Public-Private-People partnerships that engage in open innovation networks, adopting the QH approach. These networks serve as hubs

for knowledge exchange and innovation, emphasising absorptive, desorptive, and connective capacities among stakeholders. We have categorised LLs based on their driving forces: Utilizer-driven, Enabler-driven, Provider-driven, and User-driven. This stakeholder model aligns LLs with the OI paradigm, emphasising their collaborative and user-centric nature.

Moving to the meso level, we have explored LL projects within the context of LL constellations. We introduced the concept of building blocks and pillars that constitute the foundation of LL projects, highlighting technical infrastructure, ecosystem approach, openness, community, lifespan, scale, and real-world context. The LLs Integrative Process (LLIP) served as a structured and iterative framework for driving innovation, emphasising human-centric design and scalability.

Finally, at the micro level, we examined the research activities within LL projects, emphasising their alignment with the User Innovation model and User-Centred Design principles. We categorised LLs based on their innovation process characteristics and tool utilisation, highlighting four key patterns: linearizers, iterators, mass customizers, and tailors. This micro-level analysis revealed that standardised tools and processes tend to yield incremental innovations, while an iterative, non-linear approach with customised tools fosters novel and undefined innovation outcomes.

Furthermore, the chapter highlighted the strategic alignment between LLs and Horizon Europe's Missions. LLs serve as instrumental in achieving these ambitious goals by facilitating experimentation, stakeholder engagement, and the dissemination of contextually tailored solutions. This fosters knowledge exchange and empowers diverse actors, including user communities, to co-create solutions that address the multifaceted challenges outlined in the Missions.

Finally, the discussion emphasised the potential of LLs to bridge the "European Paradox" by harnessing the power of OI. Their ability to facilitate knowledge exploration and exploitation fosters a dynamic exchange that spurs innovation and translates research findings into marketable solutions. This comprehensive analysis positions LLs not just as innovation hubs, but as crucial drivers of collaborative and user-centric solutions for the complex challenges facing contemporary society.

3 Building Sustainable Living Labs: Business Models and Living Labs

3.1 What is a Business Model?

Over the past decades, the term "business model" has been frequently misused by both academics and practitioners. It is commonly employed by managers, consultants, scholars from diverse fields, and even in popular media. This widespread usage suggests the significance of Business Models (BMs), yet there is no established consensus on its precise definition (DaSilva & Trkman, 2012).

Models, including BMs, implicitly or explicitly address the internal competencies that underlie a firm's competitive advantage (Morris et al., 2005). This aligns with the resource-based view (RBV), which considers a firm as a bundle of resources and capabilities (Barney, 1991). Therefore, the RBV has significantly influenced BM research emphasising how these resources and capabilities can be leveraged to create a competitive advantage. However, the RBV alone does not account for the complexity of BMs or their recent prominence. Resources, in isolation, do not bring value to customers; value is generated through transactions utilising these resources. To address this, McIvor (2009) highlighted the importance of combining the RBV with transaction cost economics (TCE) theories: while unique combinations of resources create business value, TCE identifies transaction efficiency as a source of value for customers and the firm (Morris et al., 2005).

Supporting these findings, BMs represent specific combinations of resources that generate value for both customers and the organisation through transactions (DaSilva & Trkman, 2012; Morris et al., 2005). A BM mediates the value-creation and value-capture processes, translating between technical and economic domains by selecting and filtering innovations and technologies and packaging them into configurations offered to a target market.

This means that, whenever a business enterprise is established, it employs a particular BM, either explicitly or implicitly, describing the design or architecture of the value creation, delivery, and capture mechanisms it uses. The essence of a BM lies in defining how the enterprise delivers value to customers, entices customers to pay for that value, and converts those payments into profit. It reflects management's hypothesis about what customers want,

how they want it, and how the enterprise can best meet those needs, get paid for doing so, and make a profit (Teece, 2010).

The functions of a BM include (Chesbrough & Rosenbloom, 2002):

- Articulating the value proposition.
- Identifying a market segment—the users to whom the technology is useful and for what purpose—and specifying the revenue generation mechanisms for the firm.
- Defining the structure of the value chain within the firm required to create and distribute the offering and determining the complementary assets needed to support the firm's position in this chain.
- Estimating the cost structure and profit potential of producing the offering, given the chosen value proposition and value chain structure.
- Describing the firm's position within the value network linking suppliers and customers, including identifying potential complementors and competitors.
- Formulating the competitive strategy by which the innovating firm will gain and hold an advantage over rivals.

Therefore, we agree with Teece (2010) stating that the notion of "business models" refers primarily to a conceptual rather than a financial model of a business. It makes implicit assumptions about customers, revenue and cost behaviours, the changing nature of user needs, and likely competitor responses. A robust BM yields value propositions compelling to customers, achieves advantageous cost and risk structures, and enables significant value capture by the business generating and delivering products and services.

New BMs represent provisional solutions to user/customer needs proposed by entrepreneurs/managers. A BM is provisional in the sense that it is likely to be replaced over time by an improved model that leverages further technological or organisational innovations (Shirky, 2009).

Therefore, despite conceptual differences among researchers, some emerging themes are evident (Zott et al., 2011):

1. A BM is recognized as a distinct unit of analysis, separate from the product, firm, industry, or network. It centres on a focal firm but has boundaries that extend beyond the firm.
2. BMs emphasise a system-level, holistic approach to explaining how firms conduct business.
3. The activities of the firm and its partners are integral to various conceptualizations of BMs.
4. BMs aim to explain both value creation and value capture.

The concept of a BM is both critical and multifaceted, acting as a bridge between a firm's internal resources and external market demands. Despite varying definitions, common themes highlight its role in value creation and capture, emphasising a holistic and systemic perspective. The interplay between resource-based views and transaction cost economics underscores the complexity of BMs. Moreover, the evolving nature of BMs, driven by technological and organisational innovations, suggests that businesses must remain adaptable, continuously refining their models to align with market needs and competitive landscapes.

3.1.1 What a Business Model is Not

Having a clear understanding of the elements of a BM allows us to define what it is not.

A BM is a conceptual model rather than a financial one, making implicit assumptions about user behaviour, revenue and cost dynamics, evolving user needs, and potential competitor responses. It outlines how a company creates, delivers, and captures value (Chesbrough & Rosenbloom, 2002; DaSilva & Trkman, 2012; Teece, 2010).

Business Models and Strategy

Building on the work of Casadesus-Masanell and Ricart (2010, p. 204), who assert that “business models are reflections of the realised strategy”, DaSilva and Trkman (2012) argue that strategy plays a pivotal role in shaping the dynamic capabilities that influence the evolution of BMs. In this view, strategy is responsible for establishing dynamic capabilities that, in turn, define and limit the range of potential BMs available to address both future and current challenges. Strategy, therefore, involves the deliberate creation of these capabilities, which are

then operationalized through the organisation's BM. Consequently, BMs are constrained and shaped by the firm's dynamic capabilities. DaSilva and Trkman (2012) further highlight that strategy articulates the company's aspirations for the future, whereas BMs depict the company's current state.

Additionally, three key distinctions separate BMs from strategy. First, value creation through BMs involves a network of exchange relationships and activities among multiple stakeholders, extending beyond the internal organisation of a firm. While centred on a focal firm, BMs span firm boundaries, reflecting a broader, interconnected approach. Second, the traditional strategy focus on competition, value capture, and competitive advantage is less central to the BM concept, which emphasises cooperation, partnerships, and joint value creation (Magretta, 2002). Finally, the BM's emphasis on value propositions and the role of the customer is more pronounced than in traditional strategy literature. BMs are inherently customer-centric, revolving around the creation of value for customers (Chesbrough & Rosenbloom, 2002).

Business Models and Business Plans

The primary distinction between BMs and business plans (BPs) lies in their scope and level of detail. A BM offers a broad, high-level overview of how the business intends to operate and generate revenue, focusing on core logic and value proposition. It is a flexible tool that can be adapted as the business evolves and new information emerges. In contrast, a BP delves into granular details, providing a thorough analysis that supports operational planning, hence its structure is more rigid and requires updates as the business progresses (Cerezo Soto & Gonzalez Torres, 2024).

A BP is a comprehensive document outlining the operational and financial plans of the company. It describes the business, its objectives, strategies, the target market, and its financial forecasts. A BP includes sections such as an executive summary, company description, market analysis, organisational structure, product or service lines, marketing and sales strategies, funding requests, and detailed financial projections. It provides an in-depth roadmap covering both short-term and long-term goals, detailing the specific steps necessary to achieve these objectives (Cremades, 2018; Evans, 2015).

BMs are often developed during the early idea phase to test the viability of the business concept (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). Once validated, the BM serves as a foundation for creating a detailed BP, guiding the launch and growth phases of the company.

Business Models and Revenue Models

A “revenue model” is defined as the specific mode by which a BM enables the generation of revenue, describing the revenue sources, their volume, and distribution. While it is an important element of a BM, focusing on how value is captured by a firm, a revenue model alone does not define how a company creates value in its entirety. It solely outlines how revenue is appropriated by the firm through the sale of its goods or services. Thus, a revenue model is a crucial component of a BM but not synonymous with it (DaSilva & Trkman, 2012).

3.1.1.1 Key Distinctions and Comparative Insights into Business Model Constructs

In summary, the BM represents a novel subject of innovation, complementing the traditional focuses of process, product, and organisational innovation. It involves new forms of cooperation and collaboration, underscoring its importance in modern business strategy and operations. Understanding what a BM is not is crucial for distinguishing it from related concepts such as business plans, strategy, and revenue models. While strategy involves the long-term dynamic capabilities and competitive positioning of a firm, a BM reflects the current operational framework of the business. It is distinct from a business plan, which is a detailed, operational document outlining the steps to achieve business goals. Unlike a revenue model, which focuses solely on how a firm captures value through revenue generation, a BM encompasses the broader logic of how a business creates and delivers value to its customers. Recognizing these distinctions helps clarify the multifaceted role of BMs in modern business practice, highlighting their importance in driving innovation and strategic planning.

	Business Model	Strategy	Business Plan	Revenue Model
Definition	A conceptual framework outlining how a firm creates, delivers, and captures value.	A long-term plan defining a firm's competitive positioning and dynamic capabilities.	A detailed operational document outlining goals, steps, and financial projections for execution.	A specific component of a BM that details how a firm generates revenue.
Scope	Encompasses the entire value creation and capture process across multiple stakeholders.	Broad vision and aspirations guiding the overall direction of the firm.	Focuses on the practical execution of the business, including market analysis and funding.	Concentrates solely on the mechanisms and channels through which revenue is earned.
Focus	Emphasizes the value proposition and mechanisms for delivering and capturing value.	Prioritizes long-term competitive advantage and market positioning.	Details the step-by-step roadmap for operational success and growth.	Specifies revenue sources, volumes, and distribution methods.
Flexibility	Adaptive and iterative, evolving with changing market conditions.	Generally stable but subject to periodic review and adjustment.	More rigid; requires frequent updates as the business evolves.	Defined within the BM, with less standalone adaptability.
Time Horizon	Reflects the current operational framework with an eye on future adjustments.	Future-oriented, setting the long-term direction for the firm.	Integrates both short-term and long-term planning aspects.	Does not inherently address time horizon; focuses on revenue generation.

Table 3 - Comparison of BM, Strategy, BM and Revenue Model

3.1.2 The Crucial Interplay of BMs and Innovation

The interplay between BMs and innovation is fundamental to capturing value in today's competitive landscape. Each new product or service must be paired with a BM that outlines strategies for market entry and value capture, ensuring that innovation translates into economic success.

Chesbrough and Rosenbloom (2002) delve into the pivotal role BMs play in transforming innovations into economically viable products and services. They argue that a well-crafted BM acts as a heuristic framework, bridging the technical potential of an innovation with its economic realisation. While an effective BM can unlock significant value from technology, it may also impose cognitive constraints that limit the exploration of alternative models for future innovations. This phenomenon is illustrated through the example of Xerox Corporation where an effective BM enabled the company to successfully commercialise a groundbreaking innovation, but Xerox's reliance on this model hindered its ability to effectively manage spin-offs from its Palo Alto Research Center (PARC). These spin-offs thrived only when they adopted BMs that diverged significantly from Xerox's traditional approach, while those that clung to outdated models struggled to fully realise the value of their innovations. This case underscores the importance of flexibility and adaptation in BM development, particularly in environments characterised by high technical and market uncertainty.

History shows that without compelling value propositions for consumers and profitable business systems to satisfy them at acceptable quality and price points, even remarkable innovations will fail. This underscores the importance of management, entrepreneurship, and BM design and implementation to economic growth, alongside technological innovation (Chesbrough & Rosenbloom, 2002; Teece, 2010).

The study by Chesbrough and Rosenbloom (2002) emphasises that often the ideal BM is not immediately apparent, requiring ongoing learning and adjustments. New BMs are provisional solutions to user and customer needs, proposed by entrepreneurs and managers navigating the uncertainties of both technology and market dynamics. Given the inherent unpredictability, the full range of feasible BMs cannot be foreseen in advance. Heuristic logic is essential to discovering the appropriate BM, though an established corporation's "sense-making" process may be constrained by its dominant logic, which is rooted in its existing BM.

Another critical consideration is whether the BM itself can become a source of competitive advantage. While many components of a BM can be acquired or implemented, the interplay among these components is more challenging to replicate. A BM can confer competitive advantage if it includes systems, processes, and assets that are difficult to imitate, involves a degree of opacity, or if incumbents are reluctant to replicate it due to potential risks, such as cannibalisation of existing sales or disruption of key business relationships (Teece, 2010).

BM innovation can serve as a pathway to competitive advantage if the model is sufficiently differentiated and challenging for competitors to replicate. According to Teece (2010), for a BM to be a source of competitive advantage, it must go beyond a logical way of doing business. It must be finely tuned to meet specific customer needs and possess elements that are difficult to imitate, either due to complexity, intellectual property protections, or organisational structures that resist change. A well-designed and implemented BM considers both internal and external factors, including customer dynamics, supplier relationships, and the broader business environment.

In conclusion, the intricate relationship between BMs and innovation highlights the necessity of integrating robust commercialization strategies with innovative efforts. Technological breakthroughs alone rarely guarantee economic success without a well-designed BM to capture and deliver value effectively. Historical examples and scholarly insights demonstrate that management, entrepreneurship, and adaptive BM design are crucial for economic growth and competitive advantage. Moreover, the differentiation and complexity inherent in a successful BM can establish it as a formidable source of competitive advantage, resistant to replication by competitors. To achieve sustainable success, businesses must focus on continuously refining their BMs to meet evolving customer needs, leveraging unique processes, assets, and strategic implementations that are difficult to imitate. The dynamic interplay of these factors ultimately determines the commercial viability and enduring impact of innovations.

In the next chapter, we will analyse how BMs and their intricate dynamics apply to LLs, considered as open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments, using a user-centred iterative feedback process throughout the lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact (ENoLL - European Network of Living Labs, 2023b).

3.2 Achieving Financial Sustainability in Living Labs: A Comprehensive Approach to Business Models

Today, many Living Labs struggle to translate the value they create into a sustainable BM, resulting in widespread financial unsustainability that undermines their long-term viability (Leminen, Westerlund, & Mika, 2012; Veeckman et al., 2013).

The financial sustainability of LLs involves two aspects: first, the basic economic requirement to fund activities and the LL; and second, the responsibility to the broader community (Gualandi & L. Romme, 2019): developing solutions that improve human life and living conditions necessitates long-term financial support, rather than short-term funding (Tukiainen et al., 2015).

Studies have shown that most LLs primarily rely on public grants and subsidies (Gualandi & L. Romme, 2019). Although this may be the only short-term financing option, it does not ensure long-term viability, as many LLs cease activities once public funding ends. Additionally, the temporary nature of this funding can lead LLs to focus on capturing funds rather than adhering to their initial mission. Furthermore, public subsidy programs, such as those from the European Union, increasingly require LLs to serve private markets, often mandating a revenue share of 25% to 50% from private sources (Katzy, 2012). Finally, many LLs do not systematically use business modelling techniques to improve their cost structure, customer segmentation, and revenue streams (Mastelic et al., 2015).

The long-term sustainability of LLs hinges on their capacity to achieve autonomy and generate sufficient income through their services (Katzy, 2012).

BMs play a pivotal role in this context, as they delineate the mechanisms through which value is created and captured. BMs offer a comprehensive, high-level framework that elucidates the operational strategies and sustainability pathways of a business or organisation. Mastery and utilisation of BMs are thus essential for LLs, enabling them to systematically structure their operations, optimise value creation, and ensure long-term viability. This strategic approach underscores the importance of a well-defined BM in fostering the resilience and economic independence of LLs.

3.2.1 The Value Created in a Living Lab

As previously emphasised, the core components of a BM are the mechanisms for value creation and capture, as well as the relationship between these mechanisms. Consequently, an essential question arises: what kind of value is created in a LL?

The value generated by a LL varies in nature, affected stakeholders, and implications. Gualandi and Leonardi (2018) categorise the value into three distinct types:

Economic Value: It refers to the aggregate benefits from initiatives that emerge from collaborative, user-driven innovation processes and can often be quantified financially - such as cost reductions, improved efficiencies, and overall economic performance improvements for the innovation ecosystem (e.g. streamlined operations and reduced public expenditure through innovative, community-based solutions).

Business Value: It is focused on the returns that individual organizations or companies gain from their participation in the Living Lab ecosystem. This value is measured by factors such as: innovation and product development (e.g. accelerated development of new technologies or services), competitive advantage (e.g. enhanced market positioning) and direct financial returns (e.g. increased revenue streams, cost savings, and better return on investment from pilot projects and innovations).

Public Value: This is delivered by a LL when it supports and promotes solutions addressing local challenges and opportunities, contributing to public policy goals. Public value, while often considered the most significant output of LLs, is also more challenging to define and measure compared to economic and business values. Identifying and measuring social value remains a challenge, although some researchers and institutions are developing methodologies to assess the public value created (see 2.2.2 Impact Assessment and Evaluation of Living Labs). A well-studied situation highlighting the challenges of value capture is the investment in basic research and the production of scientific knowledge. Basic research often culminates in scientific publications, which offer limited intellectual property protection. Consequently, it is difficult to monetize discoveries, despite their high potential societal value, leading to limited investment in basic research by firms. The spillover effects are significant, making it challenging to profit from discoveries and discouraging investment in basic research. This situation is also applicable to LLs when they produce public value (Teece, 2010).

In conclusion, Living Labs present a multifaceted approach to value creation, encompassing economic, business, and public dimensions. While economic and business values are relatively easier to quantify and capture, public value poses significant challenges in measurement and valuation. The traditional revenue models are often insufficient for capturing the full spectrum of value generated by LLs, especially in the realm of public value. Therefore, innovative BMs and management principles are essential to effectively harness and distribute the diverse benefits produced. Understanding and addressing these complexities is crucial for maximising the impact of LLs on innovation ecosystems and societal well-being.

3.2.2 Key Characteristics of a Business Model for Living Labs

LLs are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of innovation to create sustainable impact. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling up innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) joint value to the involved stakeholders. At the macro level, LLs are characterised as Public-Private-People partnerships organised to facilitate knowledge exchange and conduct innovation projects (See 2.2 Living Labs in Europe). LLs necessitate BMs that accommodate and leverage these dynamic environments to foster innovation.

Integration of External and Internal Knowledge

The essence of LLs lies in the seamless integration of external and internal knowledge, resources, and capabilities. BMs tailored for these ecosystems must prioritise collaborative frameworks that support knowledge exchange and innovation across organizational boundaries. This necessitates mechanisms that facilitate the fluid sharing of intellectual property (IP) while balancing openness and protection. Flexible IP agreements, licensing arrangements, and shared patents are critical components of such BMs (Hietanen et al., 2007), ensuring that external collaborations are encouraged without compromising proprietary knowledge and competitive advantages.

Collaboration Among Quadruple Helix Stakeholders

Living labs involve collaboration among stakeholders from the QH model, encompassing academia, industry, government, and civil society (See 2.2 Living Labs in Europe). These stakeholders, with their distinct roles and interests, require BMs that promote the effective

integration and coordination of contributions towards innovation. Clear governance structures with defined roles and responsibilities, coupled with transparent decision-making processes, are crucial to managing the complex interplay of interests within the LL ecosystem (Fasshauer, 2020).

Co-Creation and User Participation

The co-creation process is fundamental to LLs, necessitating BMs that incentivize user participation. Effective models include both financial incentives, such as grants and prizes, and non-financial rewards like recognition, access to new markets, and enhanced capabilities (Spagnoli, 2023). Studies indicate that engaging in co-creation requires a shift from traditional BMs to user-centric ones. This involves redesigning key internal processes, such as R&D and marketing, to facilitate the participation of external contributors (Hienerth et al., 2011). Additionally, BMs must allow external parties to participate in specific organizational activities and adapt delivery processes to meet the increased need for customization (Storbacka et al., 2012).

Flexibility and Adaptability

The dynamic nature of LLs demands BMs that accommodate fluidity in partnerships, project scopes, and innovation directions. Modular organisational designs and agile management practices are essential to adapt quickly to new information, evolving user needs, and unforeseen opportunities (See 3.1 What is a Business Model?). This adaptability ensures that LLs remain responsive and effective in a rapidly changing innovation landscape.

Sustainability and Scalability

BMs for LLs should incorporate long-term sustainability strategies, including continuous funding mechanisms, ongoing stakeholder engagement, and iterative improvement processes. Moreover, these models must be designed to scale, accommodating increased participation and expanding innovation activities without sacrificing efficiency or effectiveness (ENoLL - European Network of Living Labs, 2023b).

Social Impact

LLs aim to address real social needs and create positive social outcomes. This objective must be reflected in the BMs, ensuring that innovation activities align with broader societal goals and contribute to meaningful social change.

Policy Support

Currently, and likely in the future, project grants and basic fixed funding dominate the revenue sources for LLs (See 3.2.2.1 The Revenue Model). However, this reliance on project grants makes LLs vulnerable to the decisions of policymakers who control the availability of suitable project calls. Hence, a long-term commitment from politicians and policymakers is essential to foster and sustain the LL movement (ProVaHealth project, 2020; Santonen et al., 2020).

Regional vs. National Structures

The structure of public funding - whether regional or national - plays a significant role in the effectiveness of Living Labs (LLs). Regional or city-driven funding approaches can foster strong connections to local innovation ecosystems, enhancing business opportunities for LLs within specific geographical areas. However, despite their potential to support cross-disciplinary collaboration, regional funding schemes are often aligned with local priorities, and administrative boundaries may limit the scope of projects. This constraint can inadvertently lead to silo effects and sub-optimization. In contrast, national funding structures generally operate on a broader scale, facilitating cross-regional and cross-disciplinary collaboration more effectively. Nevertheless, they may be less responsive to local needs and priorities, potentially reducing their impact on place-based innovation ecosystems. A study by Santonen et al.(2020) revealed that the impact of these funding structures varies, and successful outcomes depend more on execution than on the structure itself.

Geographical Location

The geographical location and the local surrounding ecosystem are critical to LL operations. Proximity facilitates easier collaboration among different organisations or LL environments. The local context can significantly influence the effectiveness and integration of LLs within the broader innovation ecosystem and therefore their long term viability (Santonen et al., 2020).

Hosting Organisations

LLs are typically hosted by various types of organisations, including universities, research organisations, public authorities, civil society organisations or private industries. Usually, the host drives the LL's activities (see 2.2.1.1 Macro Level). Therefore, the LL's BM must align with the host organisation's strategy (Santonen et al., 2020; Schuurman et al., 2024).

Partnerships

Establishing extensive partnerships is crucial for the success of LLs; indeed, partnerships often lead to customer relationships within the same customer segment type. Moreover, LLs are inherently grounded in multi-stakeholder collaboration, therefore fulfilling this requirement is anyhow essential. Consequently, LLs should strive to establish as many partnerships as possible to enhance their reach and effectiveness (Santonen et al., 2020).

The BMs for LLs must be designed to address the unique requirements of these open innovation ecosystems. Economic sustainability hinges on diversified revenue sources and long-term policy support. The structure of funding, whether regional or national and the geographical context play critical roles in the success of LLs. Additionally, the alignment with hosting organisations' strategies and the cultivation of extensive partnerships are vital for fostering robust and dynamic innovation processes. Through these tailored approaches, LLs can effectively harness the collective intelligence and creativity of diverse contributors, driving impactful and sustainable innovation.

3.2.2.1 The Revenue Model

As already underlined (see 3.1.1 What a Business Model is Not) a revenue model is a crucial component of a BM but not synonymous with it. While the revenue model focuses on how a firm captures value (Amit & Zott, 2001), it does not define how a company creates value, it only outlines how the firm generates revenue through the sale of goods or services.

The question, therefore, is: how can a Living Lab exploit the economic, business, and public value it generates to ensure the revenue streams necessary for financial sustainability? Based on their study of three different Living Labs in Italy and the Netherlands, Gualandi and Romme (2019) have classified four types of funding options for Living Labs: Pay per Service (PPS), Subsidies (SUB), Out-of-Network Funds (ONF), and Cross-Financing (CRF). These options

are complementary rather than mutually exclusive, suggesting that any LL should seek to exploit the potential of each option.

Pay per Service

Pay Per Service (PPS) is a direct monetary revenue derived from services offered by the LL. It represents the financial return on the economic value generated, primarily delivered to business partners who seek the LL's support in developing or improving their commercial products and services. While PPS is mostly sourced from the private sector, it can occasionally arise from creating business or public value, thereby shifting some funding towards the public sector. Moreover, academic institutions may also engage Living Labs on a pay-per-service basis - for example, hiring a Living Lab to conduct comprehensive user research, usability studies, or other evaluative activities. This funding option is available at the project level (meso level).

ENoLL(ENoLL - European Network of Living Labs & Vervoort, 2025) has classified various services offered by LLs, each potentially encompassing multiple sub-services for which the LL can receive payment:

- *Testing and validation services (e.g., end-user engagement, rapid prototyping, experimentation, usability, real-life testing...)*
- *Innovation network orchestration (e.g., community and network building, stakeholder mapping, stakeholder events...)*
- *Living Lab project planning and management (Living Lab as a service)*
- *Co-creation services (e.g., idea selection, facilitation workshops, focus groups, co-design...)*
- *Capacity building services (e.g., trainings, mentoring, awareness raising...)*
- *Advisory services (e.g., analytical/research services, benchmarking, foresight, regulation support...)*
- *Market and sales support (e.g., deployment services, scaling up solutions to other Living Labs...)*
- *Infrastructure and data management services (e.g., equipment and facility rental, Living Lab as research/technology infrastructure)*

Subsidies

Subsidies (SUB) are a predominant funding source provided by strategic partners to generate public and business value. These partners engage in long-term relationships with the LL to develop shared goals and objectives. Public value is delivered to citizens and stakeholders from the public sector or higher education, who compensate the LL with subsidies. Hence, SUB mainly relies on public sources and supports the entire innovation process and operations of the LL.

Out-of-Network Funds

LLs often align with the United Nations' sustainable development goals, allowing them to acquire funds by submitting proposals to supranational, national, and regional calls. Many LL projects are compatible with public policies, and open calls present opportunities to finance public value creation. Out-of-Network-Funds (ONF) are primarily provided by public bodies based on predefined criteria, with occasional contributions from private entities. ONF supports the LL's mission and relates mainly to the macro level.

Cross-Financing

Cross-Financing (CRF) is not linked to the LL's core activities but rather involves profiting from the LL's assets, such as its physical location or equipment. For instance, the LL can sublet space to a bar or co-working office, or temporarily rent it for events and meetings. Equipment can also be rented to external users for a fee. CRF is sourced almost exclusively from entities external to the LL's main operations.

Overview of Revenue Streams for Financial Sustainability

The financial sustainability of LLs hinges on the strategic exploitation of diverse funding options to capitalise on the economic, business, and public value they generate. The study by Gualandi and Romme (2019) highlights four primary funding mechanisms—PPS, SUB, ONF, and CRF—each offering distinct yet complementary avenues for revenue generation. To optimise their funding mix, LLs should categorise the value they create, align stakeholders with suitable financing options, diversify their funding sources, and balance mission-aligned and

ancillary revenue streams. Understanding the distinct characteristics and expectations of public and private funding further enhances their ability to attract and manage funds effectively, ensuring long-term viability and impact.

3.2.2.2 Cost Structure

The cost structure within a BM pertains to the comprehensive breakdown of expenses incurred by a LL during its operations. This structure encompasses the myriad costs associated with maintaining the LL and delivering its solutions or services. A thorough understanding of the cost structure is crucial for evaluating profitability, managing expenses, and formulating strategic decisions. Expenses are typically categorised into:

- *Fixed Costs*: These are expenses that remain constant regardless of the level of output, including rent, salaries, and utilities.
- *Variable Costs*: These fluctuate with production levels and include costs such as materials, production, and distribution.
- *Launch Costs*: These are initial expenses incurred during the establishment of the LL.

The ProVaHealth project (2020) highlights personnel and infrastructure costs as the most significant cost elements for LLs. Given that LL activities employ a user-centred approach, necessitating extensive interaction among diverse groups, it is unsurprising that personnel costs are paramount. LLs often engage part-time employees and experts from internal or external organisations on a temporary basis for specific tasks. This dynamic resourcing model facilitates better cost control and enables the deployment of highly qualified experts as needed.

Infrastructure and facility costs constitute the second most important cost element. LLs operate in real-life environments, which inherently increases these expenses. Therefore, it is imperative to conduct realistic calculations prior to investing in costly infrastructure and facilities, ensuring that such investments are justified by their support for LL activities (ProVaHealth project, 2020).

In conclusion, understanding the cost structure within a BM is pivotal for the effective operation and strategic management of LL. By categorising expenses into fixed costs, variable costs, and launch costs, LLs can gain a comprehensive view of their financial commitments.

Ultimately, a detailed understanding and careful management of the cost structure are fundamental to sustaining the profitability and success of Living Labs.

3.3 Business Model Canvas

A widely recognized and extensively utilised framework for BMs is the business model canvas (BMC). This strategic management tool aids entrepreneurs, managers, and organisations in visualising, designing, and innovating their BMs (Santonen et al., 2024). Overall, the BMC stands out for its simplicity, comprehensiveness, and ability to facilitate strategic discussions and innovation. For these reasons, the BMC has been considered as the most appropriate tool to design their BMs (Bertolin, 2023; Maurya, 2012; Moskovitz, 2020; Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010).

Several benefits are next described about what the BMC offers (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010):

Simplicity and clarity: the BMC provides a one-page overview of the entire BM, making it easy to understand and communicate. It breaks down the business into nine essential components, which are visually represented on a single canvas.

Holistic view: it offers a comprehensive view of the business, encompassing all critical aspects such as value propositions, customer segments, channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, key partnerships, and cost structure. This holistic perspective helps ensure that no important elements are overlooked

Flexibility and adaptability: the BMC is highly flexible and can be easily updated and modified as the business evolves. This adaptability is crucial for startups and businesses operating in dynamic environments where changes are frequent.

Visual and collaborative tool: the visual nature of the BMC makes it a powerful tool for brainstorming and collaboration. Teams can work together to fill out the canvas, fostering communication and idea sharing. This collaborative approach often leads to more innovative and robust BMs.

Focus on value proposition: by emphasising the value proposition, the BMC helps businesses to clearly define what makes them unique and how they deliver value to their customers. This focus is essential for differentiating the business in competitive markets.

Customer-centric approach: the BMC places significant emphasis on understanding customer segments and tailoring value propositions to meet their needs. This customer-centric approach ensures that businesses are aligned with market demands and customer preferences.

Efficiency and speed: creating a BM using the BMC is relatively quick compared to more detailed and lengthy BPs. This efficiency is particularly beneficial for LLs who need to iterate rapidly and test their assumptions.

Strategic alignment: the BMC helps align the strategic vision of the company with its operational activities. By mapping out the key components of the business, it becomes easier to ensure that all aspects are working towards the same goals and objectives.

Facilitates innovation: the BMC encourages creativity and innovation by allowing teams to experiment with different BM configurations. This experimentation can lead to the discovery of new opportunities and revenue streams.

Better risk management: by providing a clear overview of the business, the BMC helps identify potential risks and challenges early on. This foresight allows businesses to develop strategies to mitigate risks and navigate uncertainties more effectively.

It is important to note that the original BMC was not specifically designed for the context and objectives of LLs. Over the years, various configurations of the canvas have been developed to address different needs. These configurations are explored in the following subchapters, analysing their differences and strengths, and understanding the reasoning and processes that led to the development of the Liaison BMC for Living Labs by Bertolin in 2018.

3.3.1 The BMC by Osterwalder

The original BMC developed by Alexander Osterwalder in 2006 comprises nine critical elements that define, describe, and analyse BMs (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010):

1. **Customer Segments:** Identify the different groups of people or organisations an enterprise aims to reach and serve, emphasising the importance of understanding each segment's needs. An organisation must make a conscious decision about which segments to serve and which segments to ignore. Once this decision is made, a BM can be carefully designed around a strong understanding of specific customer needs (p.20).

2. **Value Proposition:** articulates the bundle of products and services that create value for a specific customer segment, detailing how a company addresses problems or fulfills customer needs.
3. **Channels:** detail how a company communicates with and reaches its customer segments to deliver its value proposition, encompassing communication, distribution, and sales channels.
4. **Customer Relationships:** describe the types of relationships a company establishes with its customer segments, ranging from personal assistance to automated services.
5. **Revenue Streams:** Identify the sources of cash flow from each customer segment. A company must ask itself, For what value is each Customer Segment truly willing to pay? Successfully answering that question allows the firm to generate one or more Revenue Streams from each Customer Segment.
6. **Key Resources:** lists the most important assets required to make the BM work, including physical, intellectual, human, and financial resources.
7. **Key Activities:** highlights the critical actions a company must undertake to operate successfully, such as production, problem-solving, and platform/network maintenance.
8. **Key Partnerships:** defines the network of suppliers and partners essential to the BM, including strategic alliances, joint ventures, and buyer-supplier relationships.
9. **Cost Structure:** outlines all costs involved in operating the BM, covering launch, fixed and variable costs.

Figure 6 - The Business Model Canvas

(Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010)

By integrating these elements that cover the four main areas of a business, namely customer, offer, infrastructure and financial viability, this canvas provides a comprehensive and strategic approach to how operations work, identifies areas for improvement, and innovates ways to deliver value to customers and/or users. It is a dynamic tool that can be adjusted as the business environment and market conditions change (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010).

3.3.2 The Lean BMC

Ash Maurya developed a variation of the BMC called the "Lean Canvas" (Maurya, 2012). The Lean Canvas is specifically tailored for startups and focuses on problem-solving and early-stage customer validation. Indeed, with respect to the Osterwalder BMC, Maurya replaced the four elements “Customer relationships”, “Key resources”, “Key activities”, “Key partnerships” with respectively:

Problem: identify the main problems that the target customer segments face. This section helps ensure the startup is addressing a real and significant issue.

Solution: outlines the main features or solutions that address the identified problems. This element focuses on the minimal viable product needed to solve the problems effectively.

Key Metrics: defines the key performance indicators (KPIs) that will be used to measure the startup's success and track progress. These metrics are crucial for making data-driven decisions.

Unfair Advantage: identifies the unique advantage that cannot be easily copied or bought by competitors. This could include proprietary technology, unique insights, a strong brand, or a unique BM.

PROBLEM List your customers top 3 problems	SOLUTION Outline possible solution for each problem	UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION Single, clear, compelling that turns an unaware visitor into an interested prospect	UNFAIR ADVANTAGE Something that can't be easily copied or bought	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS List your target customers and users
EXISTING ALTERNATIVES List how these problems are solved today	KEY METRICS List key numbers telling how your business is doing today	HIGH LEVEL CONCEPT List your X for Y analogy (e.g. YouTube = Flickr for videos)	CHANNELS List your path to customers	EARLY ADOPTERS List characteristics of your ideal customer
COST STRUCTURE List your fixed and variable costs		REVENUE STREAMS List your sources of revenue		

Lean Canvas is adapted from Business Model Canvas and is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Un-ported License.

LEAN CANVAS

Figure 7 - The Lean Canvas

(Maurya, 2012)

The Lean Canvas thus offers a focused approach, addressing the specific needs and challenges of startups by emphasising critical factors for early-stage success.

3.3.3 The Social Lean BMC

Later in 2013, Yeoman and Mokovitz developed a specialised BMC for social entrepreneurs, called the “Social Lean Canvas” (Moskovitz, 2020). This adaptation integrates social and environmental objectives alongside financial goals, reflecting the dual mission of social

enterprises. It incorporates all the elements from the Lean Canvas, while also addressing the unique needs and goals of social enterprises by adding two crucial components:

Purpose: clearly defines the venture's mission in terms of the social or environmental problems it aims to solve.

Impact: this unique block focuses on the measurable social and environmental outcomes the enterprise aims to achieve. It emphasises the importance of tracking and reporting impact to stakeholders.

Figure 8 - The Social Lean Canvas

(Moskovitz, 2020)

The Yeoman and Moskovitz Canvas assists social entrepreneurs in balancing financial sustainability with their social and environmental objectives. It serves as a strategic tool for designing, communicating, and refining BMs that create positive change while ensuring economic viability (Moskovitz, 2020).

3.3.4 The Liaison BMC

While all BMCs offer valuable tools for various types of entrepreneurs, none are specifically designed for a LL context. Despite some commonalities with the Lean Canvas – such as addressing problems, solutions, key metrics, and impact – key characteristics of LLs remained unrepresented, particularly in the collaborative co-creation processes that involve a diverse range of stakeholders, inherent to the nature of LLs.

To fill this gap, Bertolin developed the Liaison BMC in 2018 (Bertolin, 2023), specifically tailored to the LL environment, emphasising the importance of the actors engaged in the activities and projects of LLs.

A key characteristic of LLs, absent in other BMCs, is their role as orchestrators of the QH stakeholders within innovation ecosystems (ENoLL - European Network of Living Labs, 2023a, 2023b; Schuurman, 2015). To address this, Bertolin introduced the "Key Stakeholder" box. Stakeholders here include individuals and organisations (from the QH) involved in the strategy of the LL and management of its activities. They might not benefit directly from the solution developed by the LL but have a vested interest in it. Each stakeholder group has unique interests, concerns, and expectations regarding the LL's performance, activities, and impacts. Understanding and effectively managing relationships with key stakeholders is essential for building trust, fostering collaboration, and mitigating risks. By considering the needs and perspectives of all stakeholders, LLs can make informed decisions, enhance accountability, and create value that benefits both the organisation and its broader ecosystem.

LLs are characterised by active user involvement and an innovation process rooted in co-creation. They ensure that user feedback is not only gathered but also integrated throughout the entire innovation lifecycle (ENoLL - European Network of Living Labs, 2023b, 2023a). As this iterative co-creation process is missing in the other canvases, Bertolin added two key boxes: "User Segments" and "User Engagement." "User Segments" encompass all individuals or organisations to be involved in the LL research and co-creation activities. Users can be "Key Stakeholders" of the LL or external to the LL strategy and management. "User Engagement" refers to the strategies and initiatives employed by a LL to interact with and involve its users. This involves creating meaningful opportunities for participation, ensuring that users are actively contributing to and shaping the innovation process.

Thus, the Liaison BMC is composed of thirteen elements (Bertolin, 2023):

1. **Problems:** identifies the main problems that the LL would like to address. This section helps ensure the LL is tackling a real and significant issue. By understanding, addressing, and leveraging problems effectively, LLs can unlock new opportunities for growth and create sustainable value for stakeholders.
2. **Solutions:** outlines the main features or solutions that address the identified problems. Solutions form the backbone of a BM, serving as the means by which LL delivers value to its stakeholders and achieves its objectives.
3. **Value Proposition:** represents the promise of value that a LL provides to its stakeholders. It articulates the specific benefits and advantages that differentiate the LL's solutions or services from competitors and addresses the needs or desires of the target groups. A compelling value proposition communicates how the LL's offerings solve stakeholders' problems, fulfil their needs, or create positive outcomes, ultimately driving stakeholder engagement.
4. **Key Stakeholders:** they are the individuals or groups who have a vested interest in the success and outcomes of the LL and are often involved in the decision-making process. Each stakeholder group has unique interests, concerns, and expectations regarding the LL's performance, activities, and impacts. Understanding and effectively managing relationships with key stakeholders is essential for building trust, fostering collaboration, and mitigating risks. By considering the needs and perspectives of all stakeholders, LLs can make informed decisions, enhance accountability, and create value that benefits both the organisation and its broader ecosystem.
5. **User Engagement:** user engagement refers to the strategies and initiatives employed by a LL to interact with and involve its users. Effective user engagement fosters stronger relationships, enhances user satisfaction, and drives loyalty, ultimately leading to increased retention and advocacy.
6. **User Segments:** they are the specific groups of individuals or entities that the LL needs to involve in its research and co-creation activities. Understanding the user segments is crucial for tailoring strategies and user experiences to meet the unique requirements and preferences of each group.

7. **Customer Segments:** defines the different groups of people or organizations that will purchase the products or uptake the solutions of the LL at the end of the innovation process. They can be either stakeholders or users of the LL, or completely external to the LL and its activities, still interested in the product or solution developed. Therefore, it's essential to identify and understand the needs of each segment.
8. **Key Activities:** describes the most important actions a company must take to operate successfully. Key activities can include production, problem-solving, platform/network maintenance, etc.
9. **Key Resources:** key resources in a BM represent the critical assets, both tangible and intangible, that enable a LL to operate and compete effectively. These resources can include physical assets such as facilities, equipment, and inventory, as well as intellectual property, technology, human capital, and strategic partnerships. Key resources provide the foundation for product development, service delivery, and customer engagement, and they contribute to the LL's unique value proposition and competitive advantage.
10. **Key Metrics:** key metrics refers to the quantitative measures used to assess the performance and success of the LL.
11. **Impact:** impact refers to the broader consequences and effects of the LL's activities on various stakeholders and the environment. The impact element of a BM encompasses the social, environmental, and economic outcomes resulting from the LL's operations and decisions. By prioritising responsible and sustainable practices, LLs can maximise positive impact while minimising negative repercussions.
12. **Cost Structure:** cost structure in a BM refers to the breakdown of expenses incurred by a LL in its operations. It outlines the various expenses involved in running the LL and delivering its solutions or services (See Section 3.3.2.2)
13. **Revenue Streams:** the revenue stream of a BM outlines the different channels through which the LL earns revenue. Understanding the revenue streams is essential for determining the profitability and sustainability of the BM (See Section 3.3.2.1).

LivingLab Business Model Canvas (LIAISON)

New table

PROBLEM	KEY ACTIVITIES	VALUE PROPOSITION		USER SEGMENTS	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS
SOLUTIONS					KEY STAKEHOLDERS
	KEY RESOURCES	KEY METRICS		USER ENGAGEMENT	
		IMPACT			
COST STRUCTURE			REVENUE STREAM		

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Based on a work at <https://leanstack.com>, <https://stratagyzer.com>, <https://socialleancanvas.com>.

Figure 9 - Liaison Business Model Canvas

(Bertolin, 2023)

The Liaison BMC has been specifically tailored to align with the distinctive environment of Living Labs, providing a robust framework that fosters innovation, collaboration, and sustainable value creation. This specialised tool not only addresses the inherent limitations of traditional BM canvases but also significantly enhances the ability of LLs to achieve their objectives efficiently and effectively. Consequently, the Liaison BMC has emerged as a leading instrument in the development of BMs within the context of LLs.

However, as will be elaborated in the subsequent chapter, certain critical dimensions of LLs remain insufficiently represented within the current iteration of the Liaison BMC. These gaps highlight the need for further refinement and adaptation of the tool to ensure it fully captures the complexities and unique challenges that LLs face. The ultimate aim of this dissertation is to bridge these gaps by offering a comprehensive and operational tool that not only supports the development of robust BMs for LLs but also enhances their long-term financial sustainability

3.4 CanvasLab: A Tailored BMC for Living Labs

The Liaison BMC offers several benefits, particularly in highlighting the crucial role played by stakeholders and users involved in the activities and projects of LLs. However, it also presents some critical challenges that must be addressed. Firstly, during a workshop organised by the ENoLL in October 2023 (Cerezo Soto & Gonzalez Torres, 2024), it became evident that there remains considerable confusion about the concept of a BM and its relevance to LLs. The preceding discussions have endeavoured to clarify these issues. Secondly, the workshop revealed that the structure of the Liaison BMC is perceived as convoluted by many practitioners within LLs. The lack of clarity regarding the rationale behind the BMC's design, the sequence in which to populate it, and the appropriate information to include, has hindered its effective use. Finally, it appears that the Liaison BMC does not adequately capture some of the essential characteristics unique to Living Labs.

Therefore, a new BMC, called “CanvasLab,” has been developed to address these challenges and provide LL practitioners with a practical and user-friendly tool for business model development. CanvasLab represents an advancement, particularly in the following areas:

1. **Type of Living Lab:** As articulated by Schuurman et al. (2024) and Santonen et al. (2020), Living Labs are hosted by a diverse array of organisations, each with its own strategic priorities (see 2.2.1.1 Macro Level). It is imperative that the BM of a LL aligns with the strategy of its host organisation. Thus, when developing a BM, the Living Lab must consider the nature of its host organisation - whether it is a utilizer-driven, enabler-driven, provider-driven, or user-driven Living Lab. The type of Living Lab has a profound impact on its cost structure, revenue streams, objectives, strategies, and operations. To answer this need the “Type of Living Lab” box has been added.
2. **Mission:** While not explicitly represented in the Liaison BMC, the overarching social and societal impact of LLs is central to their mission. It is essential to continually reference this purpose when developing a BM, as it is the driving force behind LLs’ activities. Therefore, the “Mission” box has been added.
3. **Operational Context:** The operational context of LLs is grounded in real-life settings, which are integral to their functioning. A BM tailored for Living Labs should explicitly incorporate this dimension, recognizing both the challenges and opportunities that arise

from operating in real-world environments. To reflect this, the "Operational Context" box has been added and divided into two sub-boxes:

- **Challenges:** LLs face several real-world challenges that can impact their operations, effectiveness, and sustainability, including:
 - **User engagement and trust** - Encouraging sustained participation and ensuring trust among diverse stakeholders, particularly in long-term innovation projects, can be difficult.
 - **Real-world unpredictability** - Unlike controlled lab settings, Living Labs must navigate unstructured, evolving conditions that can impact experiments, co-creation, and data collection.
 - **Context-specific barriers** - Depending on the environment in which a LL operates, certain limitations may arise. For examples:
 - **Rural vs. Urban Contexts:** In rural areas, challenges may include limited digital infrastructure and lower participant availability, whereas urban settings may pose challenges related to complex stakeholder coordination, fragmented community dynamics and limited perceived agency among citizens.
 - **Settings:** LLs in hospitals, schools, or corporate environments may face different types of difficulties related to access to users, organizational resistance to change, ethical concerns in testing new solutions, as well as privacy and IP concerns.
 - **Physical and logistical constraints:** LLs relying on real-world spaces must address site-specific barriers, such as permits for urban interventions, access to public infrastructure, or coordinating multiple actors on the ground.

- **Opportunities:** Despite these challenges, operating in a real-life environment provides LLs with unique advantages that enhance their innovation capacity:
 - **Authentic user engagement and feedback** – Direct interaction with users in their natural environments leads to more relevant, user-centered innovations and higher adoption rates.

- Stronger local partnerships and networks – LLs embedded in communities can co-create solutions with local governments, businesses, and civil society, leading to stronger stakeholder buy-in and potential funding opportunities.
 - Practical validation of innovations – Testing solutions in real-life conditions enables faster iteration and refinement, ensuring that innovations are both feasible and scalable before market introduction.
 - Localized impact and adaptation – LLs have the flexibility to tailor innovations to specific community needs, whether in smart cities, rural development, or institutional settings like healthcare or education.
 - Enhanced credibility & adoption: Solutions that emerge from real-world testing have a higher chance of acceptance by end-users since they are already adapted to practical conditions.
4. Innovation Ecosystem: Living Labs operate within innovation ecosystems, each characterised by specific policies, regulations, stakeholders, and mechanisms that can either facilitate or impede their success. Recognizing and integrating this ecosystem dimension is crucial for the development of a robust and effective BM, so the “Ecosystem” box has been added. This box zooms out to the macro-level factors that influence the Living Lab, including:
- Institutional & policy frameworks: Understanding how national, regional, or EU policies impact Living Lab activities, including compliance requirements and legal constraints.
 - Funding & sustainability: Identifying available financial resources, including public funding, private investment, and collaborative financing models.
 - Systemic risks & enablers: Recognizing external conditions that may accelerate or hinder the Living Lab’s ability to operate effectively, such as economic trends, policy changes, or technological shifts.
5. Partnerships: As noted by Santonen et al. (2020) and Schuurman et al. (2024), it is essential for LLs long-term sustainability to establish and nurture as many collaborations as possible with other innovation actors and institutions. Therefore the “Key Partnership” box has been added.

Furthermore, to enhance the clarity and usability of CanvasLab, a sub-classification of both cost structure and revenue streams has been introduced, reflecting the discussions in Sections 3.2.2.1 The Revenue Model and 3.2.2.2 Cost Structure. Finally, to further facilitate its use, the revised BMC is organised with a numbered structure.

Therefore, the CanvasLab is composed of eighteen boxes:

0. Type of Living Lab: identifies the host organisation of your Living Lab—whether it is utilizer-driven, enabler-driven, provider-driven, or user-driven. This classification examines how the mission and strategic objectives of the host organisation shape the Living Lab's activities and ultimately influence its BM.

1. Mission: clearly defines the LL's mission, outlining its core objectives and the societal problems it aims to solve.

2. Problems: identifies the main problems that the LL would like to address. This section helps ensure the LL is tackling a real and significant issue. By understanding, addressing, and leveraging problems effectively, LLs can unlock new opportunities for growth and create sustainable value for stakeholders.

3. Solutions: outlines the main features or solutions that address the identified problems. Solutions form the backbone of a BM, serving as the means by which LL delivers value to its stakeholders and achieves its objectives.

4. Key Stakeholders: they are the individuals or groups who have a vested interest in the success and outcomes of the LL and are involved in the decision-making process. Each stakeholder group has unique interests, concerns, and expectations regarding the LL's performance, activities, and impacts. Understanding and effectively managing relationships with key stakeholders is essential for building trust, fostering collaboration, and mitigating risks. By considering the needs and perspectives of all stakeholders, LLs can make informed decisions, enhance accountability, and create value that benefits both the organisation and its broader ecosystem.

5. Value Proposition: represents the promise of value that a LL provides to its stakeholders. It articulates the specific benefits and advantages that differentiate the LL's solutions or services from competitors and addresses the needs or desires of the

target groups. A compelling value proposition communicates how the LL's offerings solve stakeholders' problems, fulfil their needs, or create positive outcomes, ultimately driving stakeholder engagement.

6. Customer Segments: defines the different groups of people or organizations that will purchase the products or uptake the solutions of the LL at the end of the innovation process. They can be either stakeholders or users of the LL, or completely external to the LL and its activities, still interested in the product or solution developed. Therefore, it's essential to identify and understand the needs of each segment.

7. User Segments: they are the specific groups of individuals or entities that the LL needs to involve in its research and co-creation activities. Understanding the user segments is crucial for tailoring strategies and user experiences to meet the unique requirements and preferences of each group.

8. User Engagement: user engagement refers to the strategies and initiatives employed by a LL to interact with and involve its users. Effective user engagement fosters stronger relationships, enhances user satisfaction, and drives loyalty, ultimately leading to increased retention and advocacy.

9. Key Activities: describes the most important actions a company must take to operate successfully. Key activities can include production, problem-solving, platform/network maintenance, etc. Efficiency in these activities is essential for delivering top-notch products/services, engaging stakeholders, optimizing resources, fostering innovation, and achieving strategic goals. Prioritizing operational excellence, continuous improvements, and alignment with stakeholders' needs allows LLs to bolster their competitive edge and foster sustainable growth.

10. Key Resources: key resources in a BM represent the critical assets, both tangible and intangible, that enable a LL to operate and compete effectively. These resources can include physical assets such as facilities, equipment, and inventory, as well as intellectual property, technology, human capital, and strategic partnerships. Key resources provide the foundation for product development, service delivery, and customer engagement, and they contribute to the LL's unique value proposition and competitive advantage.

11. Operational Context: This box focuses on the practical, day-to-day realities of operating a Living Lab in real-world conditions. It examines both challenges and opportunities related to the physical and social environment in which the Living Lab operates.

12. Impact: impact refers to the broader consequences and effects of the LL's activities on various stakeholders and the ecosystem. The impact element of a BM encompasses the social, environmental, and economic outcomes resulting from the LL's operations and decisions.

13. Key Metrics: key metrics refers to the quantitative measures used to assess the performance and success of the LL.

14. Innovation Ecosystem: this box zooms out to the macro-level factors that influence the Living Lab, including funding structures, regulatory frameworks, and the broader innovation landscape.

15. Key Partnerships: specifies the organisations and businesses with which the Living Lab aims to collaborate. These entities do not participate in the governance of the Living Lab and all its activities but can help the LL to achieve its objectives and fulfil its mission.

16. Cost Structure: cost structure in a BM refers to the breakdown of expenses incurred by a LL in its operations. It outlines the various expenses involved in running the LL and delivering its solutions or services (See Section 3.2.2.2 Cost Structure)

17. Revenue Streams: the revenue stream of a BM outlines the different channels through which the LL earns revenue. Understanding the revenue streams is essential for determining the profitability and sustainability of the BM (See Section 3.2.2.1 The Revenue Model).

Living Lab Business Model Canvas (CanvasLab)

Type of Living Lab		0		1	
MISSION					
PROBLEMS	2		KEY ACTIVITIES		
	9		KEY RESOURCES		
SOLUTIONS		5		VALUE PROPOSITION	
3		10		IMPACT	
OPERATIONAL CONTEXT		11		KEY METRICS	
CHALLENGES		13		USER ENGAGEMENT	
OPPORTUNITIES		16		PARTNERSHIPS	
COST STRUCTURE		17		CUSTOMER SEGMENTS	
FIXED COSTS		SUB		INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM	
VARIABLE COSTS		ONF		PPS	
LAUNCH COSTS		CRF		REVENUE STREAM	
15		8		6	
14		7		4	

Figure 10 - CanvasLab

CanvasLab addresses the limitations identified in the Liaison BMC by offering a more tailored and accessible tool for LLs' business model development. By addressing the specific elements that reflect the unique nature of LLs, CanvasLab provides a comprehensive framework that captures the distinct characteristics and challenges faced by these innovation ecosystems. The additional structuring of cost and revenue components further enhances the practical application of the CanvasLab, ensuring that it not only serves as a theoretical model but also as a user-friendly instrument for practitioners. Thus, CanvasLab represents a significant step forward in equipping LLs with the tools needed to align their business models with their strategic objectives and societal missions, while ensuring their long-term resilience and maintaining financial viability.

4 Conclusions

4.1 The Role of Business Models in Innovation and the Sustainability of Living Labs

The concept of BMs has become increasingly significant in the realm of innovation, complementing traditional areas such as process, product, and organizational innovation. BMs represent a novel domain of innovation, involving new forms of cooperation and collaboration that are essential in contemporary business strategies and operations. The intricate relationship between BMs and innovation highlights the critical need to integrate robust commercialization strategies with innovative efforts. Technological breakthroughs alone rarely guarantee economic success without a well-designed BM that effectively captures and delivers value. Both historical precedents and scholarly insights underscore that management, entrepreneurship, and adaptive BM design are essential drivers of economic growth and competitive advantage. A well-crafted BM not only differentiates a business but also establishes it as a formidable source of competitive advantage, resistant to replication by competitors. Consequently, businesses must continually refine their BMs to address evolving customer needs, leveraging unique processes, assets, and strategic implementations that are challenging to imitate.

In the context of LLs, BMs are crucial in addressing the widespread financial unsustainability that threatens their long-term viability. LLs are open innovation ecosystems situated in real-life environments, characterized by co-creation, rapid prototyping, testing, and the scaling up of innovations. These labs focus on providing joint value to stakeholders through Public-Private-People partnerships that facilitate knowledge exchange and innovation projects. However, translating the value created by LLs into a sustainable BM poses significant challenges. BMs for LLs must delineate the mechanisms through which value is created and captured, thereby ensuring long-term sustainability and economic independence.

LLs present a multifaceted approach to value creation, encompassing economic, business, and public dimensions. While economic and business values are relatively straightforward to quantify and capture, public value poses substantial challenges in terms of measurement and

valuation. Traditional revenue models often fall short in capturing the full spectrum of value generated by LLs, particularly in the realm of public value. Therefore, innovative BMs and management principles are essential to effectively harness and distribute the diverse benefits produced, thereby maximizing the impact of LLs on innovation ecosystems and societal well-being. The essence of LLs lies in the seamless integration of external and internal knowledge, resources, and capabilities. BMs tailored for these ecosystems must prioritize collaborative frameworks that support knowledge exchange and innovation across organizational boundaries. LLs also involve collaboration among stakeholders from the QH model, therefore, effective BMs must promote the integration and coordination of contributions from these diverse stakeholders, supported by clear governance structures, defined roles, and transparent decision-making processes. Additionally, the co-creation process fundamental to LLs requires BMs that incentivize user participation, necessitating a shift from traditional BMs to user-centric models. This shift involves redesigning key internal processes, such as R&D and marketing, to facilitate external contributions and adapt delivery processes for greater customization. Given the dynamic nature of LLs, BMs must be flexible and adaptable to accommodate fluidity in partnerships, project scopes, and innovation directions. Modular organizational designs and agile management practices are essential for adapting quickly to new information, evolving user needs, and unforeseen opportunities. Furthermore, sustainability and scalability are paramount, requiring BMs to incorporate long-term strategies, continuous funding mechanisms, and stakeholder engagement processes. LLs must categorize the value they create, align stakeholders with appropriate financing options, and balance mission-aligned and ancillary revenue streams to ensure long-term viability.

4.2 The Development and Contributions of CanvasLab

This research has explored the complex relationship between BMs and the sustainability of LLs, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive tool that addresses the unique challenges faced by these open innovation ecosystems. The study underscores the importance of BMs not only in creating and capturing value but also in ensuring the long-term viability of LLs. Given the complexity and dynamic nature of LLs, a well-designed BM is essential for aligning their operations with both internal capabilities and external market demands.

The development of CanvasLab, a comprehensive tool for crafting BMs tailored to the LL context, represents an advancement in this field. Building on the foundation laid by the Liaison

BMC, CanvasLab integrates crucial aspects particularly relevant to LLs. These include the key elements introduced by Bertolin (2023) - Key Stakeholders, User Segments, and User Engagement - which are central to the collaborative and co-creative processes that define LLs. However, CanvasLab extends further by incorporating additional elements that address the unique requirements of LLs:

- **Type of Living Lab** box: Recognizing the diversity of LLs and the need for their BMs to align with the strategic priorities of their host organizations.
- **Mission** box: Emphasizing the social and societal impact of LLs, which is central to their purpose and activities.
- **Operational Context** box: Addressing the real-world settings in which Living Labs operate by delineating both challenges and opportunities..
- **Innovation Ecosystem** box: Integrating the broader policy, funding, and institutional frameworks that influence Living Lab operations..
- **Partnerships** box: Underscoring the necessity of establishing and nurturing collaborations with other innovation actors and institutions, which are fundamental to the success of LLs.

Furthermore, to enhance the clarity and usability of CanvasLab a sub-classification of both cost structure and revenue streams has been introduced. This sub-classification offers a more detailed and organized approach to understanding and managing the financial aspects of LLs, which is critical for their sustainability. The revised Canvas is also organized with a numbered structure, further facilitating its use by practitioners.

This research also highlights that BM innovation can serve as a pathway to competitive advantage, particularly for LLs. According to Teece (2010), for a BM to confer a competitive advantage, it must be finely tuned to meet specific customer needs and possess elements that are difficult to imitate. The complex nature of LLs, with their emphasis on co-creation, real-life testing, and ecosystem integration, positions them well to use their BM as a form of competitive advantage. The processes and structures unique to LLs are challenging to replicate by traditional firms and organizations, making a well-crafted BM a crucial tool for their success.

4.3 Limitations and Future Research

Despite the contributions of this work, several limitations warrant discussion.

First, the concept of a business model remains a significant challenge for Living Labs practitioners. Through extensive discussions with numerous Living Lab managers via my work with ENoLL, it became clear that although the need for long-term financial sustainability is universally recognized, there is considerable uncertainty regarding its practical implementation. In many cases, the business model concept is far removed from the everyday experiences and expertise of practitioners, highlighting the necessity of cultivating a dedicated culture and a shared vocabulary around business model design within the Living Lab community. Contributing in addressing this gap was a core objective of this thesis.

Second, while CanvasLab is intentionally designed as a modular tool—enabling practitioners to begin with core elements and gradually incorporate additional layers—the overall complexity of the complete canvas may be overwhelming for those not already familiar with the underlying theoretical constructs. This suggests that a detailed, step-by-step guide is essential to support effective navigation of the tool. Moreover, systematic feedback from Living Lab managers will be crucial to iteratively refine CanvasLab so that it remains aligned with practical operational realities.

Third, although the tool has been developed based on extensive research and practical insights, the daily operational realities of Living Labs demand rapid responses to external pressures such as policy shifts and evolving stakeholder needs. In practice, many Living Labs face immediate challenges - often driven by funding constraints and external imperatives - that curtail the opportunity for long-term strategic planning. This tension between the comprehensive, strategic approach required for sustained success and the exigencies of day-to-day management underscores the need for further research.

Fourth, the applicability of CanvasLab is inherently context-dependent. A Living Lab operating in the Italian Alps, for example, may confront challenges - such as limited local infrastructure, sparse stakeholder networks, and unique resource constraints - that are markedly different from those encountered by a Living Lab in a bustling metropolis like Paris. These tangible, localized differences underscore that empirical validation across diverse geographical and cultural contexts is vital to assess the long-term robustness and generalizability of CanvasLab.

Building on the insights and limitations identified in this thesis, several promising avenues for future research emerge.

Empirical validation of CanvasLab across a wide array of Living Labs is essential. Comparative studies involving labs operating in contrasting environments will yield invaluable data on how local infrastructural and socio-economic conditions affect the tool's performance. Such research would allow for refinement of the tool's modular design to better address the distinct challenges of different operational environments.

There is also a need for developing a comprehensive, step-by-step methodological guide to accompany CanvasLab. This guide would support practitioners in navigating the tool's complexity, ensuring that even those less familiar with the theoretical underpinnings can implement it effectively. Coupled with systematic feedback from Living Lab practitioners, this iterative process would enhance the user-friendliness and practical applicability of the tool.

Finally, integrating CanvasLab with complementary frameworks offers a fruitful research direction. The recent publication by Akasaka et al. (2024) presents a Platform-level Living Lab Canvas that offers a complementary perspective on sustainable management. Comparative studies exploring the synergies between these tools could lead to the development of a unified, multi-level framework that bridges long-term strategic planning with the rapid, pragmatic decision-making required for daily operations. Additionally, the Harmonized Evaluation Framework for Living Labs (Vervoort et al., 2022) provides a structured, multi-level assessment methodology that categorizes Living Lab activities into macro, meso, and micro levels. While CanvasLab focuses on business model development, an integrated evaluation approach - drawing from this harmonized framework - could support Living Labs in measuring their maturity, impact, and sustainability over time. Given that evaluation frameworks play a crucial role in assessing strengths, identifying areas for improvement, and guiding strategic decisions, future research should explore how CanvasLab can be linked to this evaluation methodology. This would allow Living Labs not only to design financially sustainable business models but also to systematically track their progress and effectiveness within innovation ecosystems.

4.4 Final Conclusions

In conclusion, CanvasLab represents a significant advancement in aligning the operational practices of Living Labs with their strategic objectives, financial sustainability, and broader societal missions. The tool has been designed not only as a theoretical framework but as a practical instrument that Living Labs can adopt and adapt to structure their business models more effectively. By integrating key dimensions CanvasLab provides a comprehensive yet flexible approach to business model development, recognizing that Living Labs operate within dynamic, multi-stakeholder environments that require continuous evolution and strategic recalibration.

While the tool is not without limitations, its modular structure offers a progressive, step-by-step approach that allows practitioners to begin with core components and expand their strategic frameworks as their Living Labs mature. However, its full potential will only be realized through systematic testing and iterative refinement. Future validation studies across diverse Living Lab contexts will be essential in determining the adaptability and robustness of the model. Given the distinct socio-economic, regulatory, and infrastructural conditions that shape the operational realities of Living Labs, CanvasLab must remain a living framework, capable of evolving in response to practitioner feedback and emerging challenges in the innovation landscape.

Beyond its direct application, the research underpinning CanvasLab contributes to the broader discourse on business models for open innovation ecosystems. By emphasizing the role of co-creation, stakeholder engagement, and financial sustainability, this thesis reinforces the need for Living Labs to move beyond project-based financing models and develop long-term strategic frameworks that ensure their resilience and impact. Moreover, this study highlights how business model innovation itself can be a key driver of competitive advantage for Living Labs.

Nevertheless, no single framework can fully capture the complexity of Living Labs, and CanvasLab should not be seen as a one-size-fits-all solution. Instead, its effectiveness will depend on how well it is integrated with complementary tools and methodologies that address other critical aspects of Living Lab management. In this regard, the integration of business model frameworks with evaluation methodologies, such as the Harmonized Evaluation Framework for Living Labs, offers a promising direction for future research. By aligning

strategic business planning with robust impact assessment, Living Labs can better demonstrate their value to funders, policymakers, and stakeholders, ensuring their long-term legitimacy and sustainability.

Ultimately, this research lays the foundation for a more structured, strategic, and sustainable approach to Living Lab business models. As the innovation landscape continues to evolve - shaped by new technologies, regulatory changes, and shifting societal needs - Living Labs must remain agile, adaptive, and strategically oriented. The continued refinement and empirical validation of CanvasLab, in conjunction with complementary approaches such as the Platform-level Living Lab Canvas and Harmonized Evaluation Framework, will be essential for driving social innovation, fostering cross-sector collaboration, and ensuring that Living Labs can effectively navigate the complexities of today's rapidly evolving innovation landscape.

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Annex I - CanvasLab

Type of Living Lab						0	
MISSION						1	
PROBLEMS	KEY ACTIVITIES		VALUE PROPOSITION		KEY STAKEHOLDERS		INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM
SOLUTIONS	KEY RESOURCES	IMPACT	USER SEGMENTS	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS			
			USER ENGAGEMENT				
		KEY METRICS	PARTNERSHIPS				
OPERATIONAL CONTEXT							
CHALLENGES	OPPORTUNITIES						
COST STRUCTURE						REVENUE STREAM	
FIXED COSTS	VARIABLE COSTS	LAUNCH COSTS	SUB	ONF	PPS	CRF	

